
Research

The Impact of the U.S.-China Trade War on the Economy in Uganda

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Abstract: The trade war that erupted in 2018 originated from the United States imposing tariffs on Chinese goods and establishing trade barriers. This economic conflict affected global supply chains. Although Uganda did not directly participate in the war, its export sector was impacted. The purpose of this research is to explore the theoretical and empirical references for Ugandan policymakers and businesses to make informed choices about the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on Uganda's economy, trade, and investment from 2018 to 2021.

Grounded on the theoretical framework of economic trade wars, the literature review reflects the development of Uganda's economy and its impact. Different from other academic research, this research delves into empirical study to precisely identify the exact consequences of the U.S.-China trade war on Uganda's economy. Utilizing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, the research further analyzes the short-term and long-term effects of trade disputes on key economic indicators, obtaining relevant evidence that promotes decision-making.

The research results indicate that the U.S.-China trade war has had a complex impact on Uganda's economy. Uganda's exports of goods to China have positively influenced the economy, while imports from both China and the United States also make a positive contribution due to Uganda's reliance on imported capital goods. Fluctuations in trade flows, particularly US exports to China and imports from China, have a positive effect on the growth of Uganda's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). On the other hand, rising prices and depreciation of the exchange rate have negatively affected the Uganda economy. Therefore, the study amends the first hypothesis that the U.S.-China trade war negatively impacts the growth of Uganda's GDP. The second hypothesis is that deviations in exchange rates, trade flows, prices, and investment flows negatively affect the growth of Uganda's GDP. Utilizing the ARDL approach, the research confirms that deviations in trade flows, investment flows, exchange rates, and prices negatively impact GDP growth.

This research identifies the industries or products where Uganda has a competitive advantage or increased demand due to trade disruptions, thereby revealing specific trade opportunities for Uganda brought about by the U.S.-China trade war. This information can help businesses and policymakers focus on areas that may benefit from the trade war and explore new trade routes. It makes this thesis a unique and valuable contribution within the literature on the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on emerging economies.

Keywords: Trade war, Gross Domestic Product, Trade flows, Exports, Investment, Economic growth, Inflation, Exchange rates

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Introduction

The U.S.-China trade war, as described by Kapustina et al (2020), was a trade conflict between the United States and China that began in 2018. This war has far-reaching implications on the worldwide economy. These two leading economies are involved in a reactive tariff battle. Each nation is imposing tariffs on goods that are imported from the other. This war has caused significant disturbances in the global trade. Numerous nations are being trapped in the crossfire. African nations have never been immune to the implications of this trade war (Fang et al., 2020). This research paper seeks to investigate the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy of Uganda.

Background of the study

Uganda is a landlocked nation which is situated in the Eastern part of the African continent. This nation has an estimated population of over 44 million people (World Bank Group, 2021). This nation depends heavily on the agricultural sector which offers nearly a quarter of the republic's gross domestic product and this makes available for over 70% of employment. According to United Nations Development Programme (2022), the economy of Uganda has been on the rise in recent years with a yearly growth rate of close to six percent between the years 2016 to 2019. Nevertheless, Uganda remains subjected to external shocks that include the commodity price changes and disruptions on the global trade.

The trade war between U.S.A and China has had a substantial impact on the global trade patterns, with these two nations imposing tariffs on each other's goods. The United States of America has targeted a variety of Chinese exports. These exports comprise of consumer goods, steel and aluminum. China has reacted by imposing tariffs on United States goods such as motor vehicles, aircraft and soybeans (Fang et al, 2020). These tariffs have widespread effects on the economy, forcing businesses to adjust to higher prices and disruptions in supply chains.

Since 2018, the United States and China, which are the world's two largest economies, have been involved in a trade war. The war began when the United States began putting taxes on Chinese goods, accusing China of unfair economic practices and seizing American intellectual property. China responded by putting taxes on American imports. This trade war has had extensive consequences for both countries as well as the world's economy.

The trade war has affected other nations other than the United States and China, for instance Uganda. The tariffs imposed on a wide range of Chinese goods, triggered retaliatory measures from China. The subsequent escalation of tariffs between the two economic giants has disrupted global supply chains, increased trade barriers and created uncertainty in international markets. While Uganda may seem distant from this conflict, its economy is not immune to its consequences. As a developing nation that is heavily reliant on international trade, Uganda's export-oriented sectors, such as agriculture and manufacturing, have been particularly vulnerable to the disruptions caused by the trade war.

Uganda has and is not directly involved in the trade war between the United States and China, but the nation state has been affected by the indirect impacts of the conflict. Uganda exports a wide variety of supplies such as tobacco, tea and coffee which are subject to the international prices in the market (Hisali, 2006). The trade war has disturbed global trading patterns, leading to a slowdown in the growth of most economies worldwide. This has a knock-on consequence on Ugandan exports demand. Moreover, the trade war has steered a universal sense of uncertainty in the global markets. This in turn discourage investment and as a result slows down economic growth.

Given the significance that agriculture has to the economy of Uganda, any disturbance to the international trade patterns will have weighty effects on the nation's growth projections. This paper will look at the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy of Uganda. It will examine the impacts of the variations in the global demand for Ugandan exports, as well as the effects of increased trade uncertainty on investment and growth. By giving a comprehensive enquiry of the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on Uganda, this paper seeks to contribute to an improved understanding of the global economic outcomes of this conflict.

Significance of research

The impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy of Uganda is a crucial area of research due to its substantial implications for the economic growth and development of the country. This study aims to examine how the trade war has affected Uganda and how Uganda has responded to mitigate the adverse consequences. By understanding the impact of the trade war, policymakers can develop policies to offset these negative effects, and companies can make informed investment and trade decisions.

Economic Significance

Uganda's economy heavily relies on international trade, especially in agricultural products such as coffee, tea and tobacco. The U.S. and China are major global players in agricultural trade, and any disruptions in their trade relationship indirectly affect Uganda's exports. Additionally, as Uganda imports a significant portion of its capital goods and raw materials from China and the U.S., trade barriers and higher tariffs can lead to increased costs, impacting overall economic growth and development.

It is crucial to study the impact of the trade war on the Ugandan economy to understand the extent of the damage caused and develop strategies to mitigate the negative effects. By doing so, policymakers can make informed decisions that can help support affected industries and reduce the impact of the trade war on the economy. Additionally, businesses can use this information to adjust their operations and seek alternative markets to minimize the effects of the trade war. Overall, by understanding the impact of the US-China trade war on the economy in Uganda we can work towards finding solutions to minimize its negative effects and promote economic stability in the nation.

Social Significance

The trade war between the United States of America and China does not only have economic implications but also has weighty social repercussions for the Ugandan residence. The increase in the cost of living has made it hard for the citizens to meet the expense of basic necessities such as food, education and healthcare. This therefore led to a rise in poverty levels and also made it difficult for the public to have access to essential services. Moreover, the U.S.-China trade war has led to a drop in foreign investment, which led to fewer job opportunities for Ugandans. Having an insight in the social implications of the trade war is essential for policymakers and stakeholders to develop targeted interventions that can defend and support those that are most affected by the disruptions.

Academic Significance

From an academic viewpoint, studying the impact of the trade war between the United States of America and China on Uganda delivers valued insights into the dynamics of the global trade and its impacts on Africa. Uganda is an applicable and interesting nation to study in the setting of the U.S.-China trade war since it is an emerging economy that is heavily reliant on exports. Uganda mainly exports coffee, tea, and other agricultural products, which are susceptible to oscillations in global prices and demand. The trade war has disturbed the global trade patterns and made new challenges for emerging economies such as Uganda. By carrying out a study on the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on Uganda, this helps to gain a better understanding of how emerging nations are affected by the global trade tensions and discover potential policy responses to alleviate the adverse consequences. This work can fund to the existing body of knowledge by creating empirical evidence particular to Uganda's setting and notifying future research on the trade policy, global governance and economic development.

Research Methodology

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model will be used in this paper. The ARDL model is a good fit because it allows for the analysis of both the short and long-term dynamics of the trade war on Uganda's economy. Additionally, the ARDL model uses cointegration analysis to find long-term relationships between variables. By estimating the ARDL model, the paper will quantify the extent of the trade war. Data for the study will be collected from reliable sources. This will ensure reliability and validity. Conclusions and hypothesis testing will be drawn from the ARDL model.

Research Content

The following sections will be included:

Chapter One: Introduction

The introductory chapter provides a contextual overview of the research topic, clearly identifies the specific issue or gap in knowledge that the study aims to address, states the main objectives of the study, highlights the importance and potential impact of the research and describes any unique or novel aspects of the study.

Chapter Two: Literature Review

In the literature review section the theoretical underpinnings and concepts pertinent to the research topic are presented. The research reviews possible policy ramifications and also looks at ways to lessen the trade wars detrimental effects on developing economies especially those in Africa. Furthermore, it looks at how the conflict might affect Uganda's trade dynamics. Additionally it examines the body of research on the impact of the trade war on developing nations and pinpoints the precise knowledge gap that the current study seeks to fill.

Chapter Three: Research Methodology

A comprehensive strategy and plan for carrying out the research is outlined in the research methodology chapter. The procedure for collecting data is explained along with the particular tools or strategies that were employed. The study's variables are precisely defined. The research data's sources and locations are identified in this chapter. It describes the diagnostic tests carried out and the model that was used for analysis. Research-related ethical issues are covered including informed consent and data privacy. The limitations or restrictions of the study are acknowledged in this chapter.

Chapter Four: Empirical Analysis

Descriptive statistics are provided to give summary measures that characterize the primary features of the data in the chapter on empirical analysis. Correlation coefficients between variables are shown in the correlation matrix so that their relationships can be examined. Tests for serial correlation and heteroscedasticity are performed as diagnostic procedures. Lastly, an analysis of the trade wars impact on Uganda's economy is conducted using the ARDL model.

Chapter Five: Discussion, Recommendations, and Conclusions

The discussion section presents the findings and analysis of the empirical analysis along with their implications. On the basis of the research findings, recommendations for policymaker's, stakeholders or additional study are made. In conclusion the study's main findings are outlined, the research objectives are reiterated and concluding remarks are made.

Research Purpose

Having a thorough understanding of the effects of the trade war on Uganda's economy is the main goal of the research. Uganda is exposed to the trade wars disruptions because it is a developing country that depends significantly on foreign trade.

The research on the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on Uganda's economy aims to understand the specific challenges and opportunities that have emerged from this ongoing conflict. By analyzing the consequences at an individual country level, policymakers, economists and stakeholders can gain a better understanding of the strategies necessary to mitigate adverse effects and optimize potential benefits.

Research Objectives

1. To inspect the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy of Uganda.
2. To recognize the specific channels through which the trade war affects Uganda's economy, such as fluctuations in trade flows, investment flows, inflation and exchange rates.
3. To assess the extent of the impact of the trade war on Uganda's Gross Domestic Product growth.
4. To shed light into the possible economic effects of the U.S.-China trade war and suggest policy measures to lessen any negative impact.

Research questions

1. What is the effect of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy of Uganda?
2. Which specific channels through which the U.S.-China trade war affects Uganda's economy are significant, such as changes in trade flows, inflation, investment flows and exchange rates
3. To what extent does the U.S.-China trade war impact Uganda's GDP growth?
4. What are the possible economic implications of the U.S.-China trade war on Uganda, and how can policy decisions mitigate any negative effects?

Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: The U.S.-China trade war affects Uganda's gross domestic product growth negatively.

Hypothesis 2: Deviations in exchange rates, trade flows, prices and investment flows have a negative impact on Uganda's Gross Domestic Product growth.

Problem Statement

With possible repercussions for developing nations like Uganda, the trade war between the United States and China has had a significant impact on the world economy. Uganda's economy which is still in its early stages of development and largely dependent on exports to sustain economic growth is therefore affected by trade agreements or the country's access to international markets. There is a need to understand the potential impact of the U.S.-China trade war on Uganda's economy, particularly regarding reduced exports, declines in global commodity prices and reduced foreign investment. Therefore, this paper aims to investigate the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy of Uganda and provide insights into the potential challenges and opportunities for policymakers and stakeholders to address

Research innovation

This paper will make several innovative contributions to the existing literature. Its unique approach lies in the comprehensive examination of specific channels through which the trade war affects Uganda's economy, such as trade flows, inflation and exchange rates. By utilizing the ARDL model, the study provides a nuanced understanding of the relationship between the trade war and Uganda's economic indicators, offering dynamic analysis that considers both short-term and long-term effects. Through quantitative assessment, the paper quantifies the impact of the trade war on Uganda's GDP, providing rigorous evidence beyond anecdotal observations. Additionally, the study offers valuable insights into potential economic implications and proposes context-specific policy recommendations to mitigate adverse effects, contributing both to academic scholarship and informing policymakers.

Delimitations of the study

The study is focused on the period between the year 2018 and 2021. The paper is enclosed to the subsequent areas.

The study is specifically focused on examining the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy of Uganda. It looks at how Uganda's economy has been impacted by this trade dispute in different areas. The study however does not broaden the scope to other nations. Focusing exclusively on Uganda, the study seeks to offer a comprehensive comprehension of the trade wars effects on this specific economy.

This research study depends only on secondary data sources, which comprise of reports and statistical data from academic institutions, international organizations and the governmental agencies. Primary data collection methods like surveys and interviews are not considered.

The study is delimited to the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy of Uganda, particularly regarding reduced exports, declines in global commodity prices and reduced foreign investment.

It is important to note that these delimitations are necessary to maintain the focus and scope of the study and ensure that the research questions are adequately addressed. However, these delimitations may also limit the generalizability of the study's findings to other contexts or time periods.

Assumptions of the study

The secondary data sources that are used are accurate and reliable. It is also assumed that the data gathered from the various sources is valid and is a representative of the Ugandan situation and the international trade environment. According to the study, Uganda's economy is significantly impacted by the trade war between the United States and China. Additionally it is assumed that Uganda has seen statistically significant effects from the trade war on exports foreign investment and commodity prices.

Another assumption is that the impact of the trade war has negative consequences on the economy of Uganda. It is also assumed that the trade war has triggered economic disturbances and challenges for Uganda and that the undesirable impacts overshadow any possible positive effects.

The study also assumes that the economic settings in Uganda continued to be relatively unchanging during the period of the study, with the exception of the impact of the U.S.-China trade war. The paper also assumes that other elements, like domestic policies or global economic trends, lacked a substantial impact on the economy of Uganda during the period of the study.

Lastly, the study assumes that the outcomes from the study can be generalized to other emerging economies that are very reliant on exports and susceptible to external economic shocks.

Chapter Summary

This section of the dissertation covered a range of important aspects related to the research study. Explicitly, the researcher offers an introduction to the study, comprising of the background and the problem statement that reinforce the research. The study purpose is also conferred, along with the research objectives and the research questions that will direct the investigation. Study delimitations are also recognized, comprising of the geographical, data, economic, timeframe and scope delimitations.

With this footing laid, the next segment of the research paper will offer a synopsis of the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the Ugandan economy. This paper will investigate the numerous means in which the trade war has affected the economy of Uganda, including export reduction, commodity price increase and foreign investment reduction. The investigator will scrutinize the data available and literature to find the precise impacts of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy of Uganda, and will discuss the consequences of these outcomes for stakeholders, policymakers and the broader global community. Through this inclusive examination, the investigator targets to shed light on the multifaceted impacts of the U.S.-China trade war on Uganda, and to offer insights that can notify decision-making and policy development in this setting.

Literature Review

This chapter aims to investigate the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the Ugandan economy, with a particular emphasis on trade, investment and economic growth. Therefore, by appraising relevant literature pertaining to the topic, this paper aims to offer a comprehensive analysis on how the U.S.-China trade war has affected the economy of Uganda and identify the crucial opportunities and challenges faced by the nation in the setting of this global trade conflict.

The trade war between the United States and China has been one of the most momentous global economic developments in recent times. The war began in 2018 as a result of the United States' discontent with China's trade practices. Since then, tensions have risen, with both nations placing tariffs worth billions of dollars on each other's goods (Liu, Zhang and Vortherms, 2022). As a result, the trade war has had a tremendous economic impact on Uganda.

Theoretical foundation

The theoretical framework offers the conceptual foundations for appreciating the influence of the U.S.-China trade war on the Ugandan economy. In this segment, we will appraise the pertinent frameworks and economic theories that are generally used to examine the impacts of trade disputes on emerging markets. By synthesizing and scrutinizing the pertinent literature, this division purposes to deliver a theoretical framework for appreciating the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy of Uganda and to find the key features that may sway the nation's economic performance in the environment of this global trade clash.

1. Theories of trade diversion and creation

Trade diversion and trade creation are the two important notions in the theory of international trade that are applicable in understanding the influence of the U.S.-China trade war on the Ugandan economy. Trade diversion happens when an economy shifts its imports from a more efficient foreign supplier to a less efficient domestic supplier as a consequence of a trade barrier (such as a tariff) that raises the price of the foreign goods (Mattoo et al, 2019). On the other hand, trade creation happens when a trade barrier promotes trade between nations that were formerly excluded from each other's markets, ensuing in greater productivity and welfare gains (Nguyen, 2019).

The U.S.-China trade war has triggered the imposition of tariffs on many goods traded between the two nations, which has caused both trade diversion and trade creation effects. For instance, the tariffs levied by the U.S. on Chinese goods have caused some U.S. importers to move their procurements to other nations (Evans, 2019). This includes Uganda, which has witnessed an upsurge in exports of certain products to the U.S. market. Nonetheless, the trade war has also disturbed the global value chains and led to upper costs for companies in both economies. This can have negative impacts on trade and economic growth in Uganda and other emerging republics.

Numerous papers have scrutinized the influence of trade diversion and trade creation on emerging economies in the setting of trade disputes and other trade policy variations. For instance, a study by Kox and Rojas-Romagosa (2019) established that trade diversion effects controlled trade creation effects in emerging nations, signifying that the negative impacts of trade barriers are greater than the positive impacts of increased trade. A different research study conducted by Carrère and Strauss-Kahn (2014) established that trade diversion bearings were predominantly strong in sub-Saharan Africa region, where most nations are heavily reliant on exports of primary supplies and have restricted diversification in their export markets.

However, it is important to note that the trade war has also disrupted global value chains and increased costs for companies in both economies. This has potential negative implications on trade and economic growth not only for Uganda but also for other emerging economies. Therefore, while trade creation opportunities may arise for Uganda in certain sectors, the overall impact of the trade war on Uganda's economy needs to be assessed comprehensively.

In light of this theory and research findings, it is crucial to evaluate the specific channels through which the U.S.-China trade war affects Uganda's economy. This entails analyzing fluctuations in trade flows, investment flows, inflation and exchange rates as key indicators of the trade diversion and creation effects. Assessing the extent of the impact on Uganda's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth and examining the hypotheses that the trade war has a

negative impact on GDP growth and that deviations in trade flows, investment flows, exchange rates, and inflation significantly affect Uganda's GDP level will provide valuable insights into the economic implications of the trade war for Uganda.

By understanding the trade diversion and creation effects within the broader context of economic globalization, policymakers can make informed decisions aimed at mitigating any adverse effects and capitalizing on potential opportunities arising from the U.S.-China trade war.

2. Comparative advantage theory

The concept of comparative advantage was first introduced by David Ricardo. The theory suggests that countries will benefit from specializing in the production of goods or services that they can produce more efficiently or at a lower opportunity cost. This theory forms the foundation of international trade, as countries engage in mutually beneficial exchanges based on their respective comparative advantages. In the context of the U.S.-China trade war, the concept of comparative advantage plays a significant role. As the two largest economies in the world, the United States and China possess unique comparative advantages in various industries. The trade war, driven by the desire to protect domestic industries, disrupts the established patterns of trade and challenges the principles of comparative advantage. The U.S.-China trade war has disrupted this concept by imposing tariffs on each other's goods. This has led to a decrease in trade between the two countries, which has affected countries that rely on exports to these two countries, including Uganda.

The theory of comparative advantage is one of the key essential concepts in the theory of international trade (Fetzer and Schwarz, 2019). According to this theory, nations must concentrate in producing goods and offering services that they have a lower opportunity cost. Opportunity cost is the cost of producing one good in terms of the forgone production of another good. This will be a comparison with other nations. On the other hand, they must trade with other nations to get goods and services which they cannot produce efficiently. That means, by specializing nations can attain higher levels of throughput and wellbeing than they will achieve in a closed economy.

The U.S.-China trade war has disrupted global supply chains and trade patterns (Fajgelbaum and Khandelwal (2022)). This can have implications on Uganda's comparative advantage in certain industries. For instance, China is a major producer of textiles and apparel (Wang et al, 2017). Hence, the imposition of tariffs on these goods by the U.S. can lead to an increase in demand for similar products from other nations, including Uganda. Conversely, the trade war can also lead to higher costs for businesses in both nations. This can reduce efficiency and productivity and limit the gains from trade.

Numerous studies have looked at the impact of comparative advantage on emerging economies in the context of international trade. For instance, a research study conducted by Hausmann and Rodrik (2003) found out that economies with more export diversification inclined to have upper levels of welfare and economic growth than the ones that specialized in a narrow range of products. Imbs and Wacziarg (2003) from their work found out that nations that specialized in industries with higher productivity inclined to have higher economic growth levels over the long term.

3. Dependency theory

The Dependency Theory is a critical approach to the study of international trade and development that highlights the unequal power relations between established and emerging economies (Farny, 2016). According to this theory, emerging economies are dependent on developed economies for resources, markets and capital, which perpetuates their underdevelopment and limits their ability to achieve economic welfare and growth. In the context of international trade, the Dependency Theory suggests that emerging nations are often forced to specialize in low-value-added primary commodities and rely on imports of high-value-added manufactured goods, further reinforcing their structural dependence on established nations (Gay, 2021).

The U.S.-China trade war has brought attention to the unequal power relations between established and emerging nations, which may have implications for Uganda's dependence on industrialized nations for investment and trade. For instance, the trade war can result in reduced demand for Uganda's exports in developed nations. Conversely, it can lead

to decreased foreign investment in the country as companies relocate their operations to other countries. These factors can negatively impact Uganda's economic growth and perpetuate its structural reliance on established nations.

The core arguments of the Dependency Theory revolve around the unequal relationship between developed and developing countries in economic globalization. Developed countries, with their economic and political influence, shape the terms of trade and dictate the rules of the global economic system, creating unfavorable trade conditions for developing countries (Adebayo, 2017). This can include low prices for their exports and high prices for imported goods and technologies.

Additionally, the Dependency Theory suggests that economic globalization hampers the industrialization and diversification of developing countries' economies. Developing countries are often compelled to specialize in producing primary commodities or low-value-added goods, making them vulnerable to fluctuations in global commodity prices and leaving them exposed to economic crises (Amsden, 2003).

Furthermore, the Dependency Theory highlights the role of foreign direct investment (FDI) from developed countries in perpetuating dependency. Multinational corporations (MNCs) from developed countries exert significant control over production facilities and resources in developing countries, extracting profits and repatriating them to their home countries. This limits the ability of developing countries to retain and reinvest profits locally, hindering their economic development (Abay, 2022).

Numerous studies have examined the impact of the Dependency Theory on emerging nations in the context of international trade. For example, Cardoso and Faletto (1979) argued that the structure of the global economy perpetuated the underdevelopment of Latin American nations by controlling their access to technology and capital and forcing them to specialize in low-value-added primary commodities. Another study conducted by Li and Li (2018) found that reliance on foreign trade and investment had negative implications for economic growth in emerging nations, particularly during global economic crises.

In summary, the Dependency Theory provides critical insights into the unequal power relations and dependency between developed and developing nations in economic globalization. It emphasizes the limitations and imbalances faced by developing countries, such as unfavorable trade conditions, hindered industrialization and a reliance on foreign investment. The U.S.-China trade war serves as an example of how these dynamics can affect emerging economies like Uganda, highlighting the need for a more equitable and sustainable global economic system.

4. Political economy theory

Political economy theories are focused with the relationship between politics and economics, and how this relationship shapes economic outcomes (Serrat, 2017). In the setting of international trade, political economy theories put emphasis on the role of power in influencing trade outcomes and trade policy. There are many political economic theories that are applicable in understanding the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the Ugandan economy including theories of hegemony, mercantilism and protectionism.

The U.S.-China trade war has been driven in part by political and strategic considerations, as well as economic ones (Fajgelbaum and Khandelwal, 2021). This can have consequences on Uganda's position in the global political economy. For instance, the trade war can cause a change in the global power dynamics. With some analysts like Murphy (2022) proposing that China may pursue to affirm greater stimulus in emerging nations like Uganda as a way of counteracting the United States of America influence. The trade war may also rise protectionism and mercantilism. This can limit Uganda's access to the global markets and shrink its potential benefits from trade.

Numerous studies have investigated the influence of political and economic factors on international trade and development. For instance, Gilpin (1987) conducted a study that claimed the hegemonic stability theory could clarify how the international economic system remained stable after World War II, where the United States played a leading role. This theory suggests that the stability of the system results from the dominant role of the leading power, which acts as a stabilizing force. On the other hand, another study by Rodrik (2018) indicated that mercantilist policies were

becoming increasingly prevalent in the global political economy. This trend could potentially create difficulties for developing countries that depend on exporting their products to other countries. Mercantilism is an economic policy that favors exports and seeks to limit imports, which could lead to protectionism and trade barriers that could negatively impact developing countries' trade and economic growth.

5. International finance theory

International finance theories are focused on the flow of capital across borders and how it moves economic outcomes (Avdjievet al, 2014). This theory highlights the significance of exchange rates and financial flows in shaping trade patterns and outcomes. Several international finance theories are applicable to understanding how the U.S.-China trade war affects Uganda's economy, such as theories that explain exchange rate determination, capital flows and currency crises. These theories aim to provide insights into the potential effects of changes in exchange rates and financial flows on Uganda's trade patterns and economic growth resulting from the ongoing trade tensions between the United States and China.

The ongoing trade war between the United States and China has the potential to impact Uganda's economy in various ways. Particularly in terms of exchange rates and financial flows. For instance, the trade war may lead to heightened fluctuations in exchange rates, which could affect Uganda's export competitiveness. This could either increase or decrease the demand for Uganda's exports, depending on the direction of exchange rate movements. Additionally, the trade war could also result in changes in global capital flows, which could limit Uganda's access to foreign investment and financing. This could have a significant impact on Uganda's economic growth and development, as foreign investment and financing are often critical sources of funding for businesses and infrastructure projects in developing countries like Uganda.

Numerous research studies have investigated the effects of international finance factors on international trade and development. For instance, Obstfeld and Rogoff (1995) conducted a study demonstrating that exchange rate movements could have a considerable impact on trade patterns and outcomes, particularly during currency crises. Conversely, Prasad and Rajan's (2008) research found that capital flows could have both favorable and unfavorable effects on economic growth and development, depending on the nature and direction of the flows. These studies offer valuable insights into the possible implications of international finance factors on Uganda's economy, given its reliance on exports and foreign investment and financing.

6. Protectionism theory

Protectionism is a theory that argues for restricting trade to protect domestic industries. This theory is often used by countries to protect their domestic industries from foreign competition. The U.S.-China trade war is an example of protectionism, where both countries have imposed tariffs on each other's goods to protect their domestic industries (Zahoor et al, 2023). However, this has led to a decrease in trade between the two countries, which has affected other countries that rely on exports to these two countries, and importing from these two countries, including Uganda.

Examining the U.S.-China trade war through the lens of protectionism theory provides insights into the potential economic implications for Uganda. The negative impact on Uganda's GDP and deviations in trade flows, investment flows, exchange rates and inflation can provide empirical evidence to support the hypotheses that the trade war has adverse effects on Uganda's economy.

Understanding the theoretical implications of the U.S.-China trade war on Uganda's economy allows for the formulation of appropriate policy decisions to mitigate any adverse effects. By considering the principles of protectionism theory and the specific challenges faced by Uganda, policymakers can develop strategies to diversify trade partners, promote domestic industries, attract alternative investment sources and enhance economic resilience in the face of global trade conflicts.

7. Neoclassical theory

The neoclassical theory of economic globalization emphasizes the benefits of free trade and market liberalization. According to this perspective, when countries engage in international trade, they can take advantage of comparative advantage, which refers to the ability of a country to produce goods or services at a lower opportunity cost than other countries (Siddiqui, 2015). Neoclassical economists argue that when countries specialize in producing goods or services in which they have a comparative advantage and engage in trade, overall efficiency and productivity increase (Murdock, 2020).

The neoclassical theory posits that liberalizing trade between nations promotes specialization, as countries focus on producing the goods or services in which they have a comparative advantage. This specialization allows countries to allocate their resources more efficiently, resulting in increased productivity and economic growth. By accessing larger markets through international trade, countries can benefit from economies of scale, leading to lower production costs and increased competitiveness (Bernardina et al, 2022).

Furthermore, neoclassical economists argue that international trade fosters competition, which drives innovation and technological advancements. When countries are exposed to global competition, domestic industries are incentivized to improve their efficiency, invest in research and development, and adopt new technologies. This process of technological progress can result in higher productivity levels and economic growth (Fagerberg et al, 2010).

The neoclassical theory also emphasizes the importance of market efficiency. By removing barriers to trade, such as tariffs and quotas, resources can flow more freely across borders, allowing markets to allocate resources based on supply and demand. This efficient allocation of resources leads to optimal outcomes, as prices reflect the true value of goods and services, and market forces drive economic decisions (Capoani, 2023).

Overall, the neoclassical theory of economic globalization suggests that liberalizing trade and embracing free market principles can result in efficiency gains, increased productivity and overall economic growth for countries participating in the global economy.

8. Economic globalization theory

Economic Globalization Theory offers a comprehensive framework for comprehending the complex dynamics and power relationships that shape the global economy (Gopinath, 2012)). At its core, this theory recognizes and emphasizes the interconnectedness of nations, highlighting the intricate web of economic interactions through trade, investment and the movement of capital.

One of the fundamental premises of Economic Globalization Theory is that the global economy is characterized by an ever-increasing level of interdependence (Shangquan, 2000). This interdependence is facilitated by advancements in technology, transportation and communication, which have significantly reduced barriers to the movement of goods, services and financial resources across national borders. Economic Globalization Theory acknowledges that these developments have led to a heightened level of integration among economies worldwide (Buckley and Ghauri, 2004).

Moreover, Economic Globalization Theory recognizes the role of global institutions in governing and regulating the global economy (Lang, 2006). Institutions such as the World Trade Organization (WTO), International Monetary Fund (IMF) and World Bank play critical roles in setting rules, norms and standards that govern international trade, finance and development (Woods, 2008). These institutions influence the behavior of nations and help shape the economic relationships between developed and developing countries.

A key aspect of Economic Globalization Theory is the examination of economic dependencies between developed and developing countries (Heller et al, 2009). It acknowledges that the global economy is marked by asymmetrical power relations, with developed nations typically holding a greater share of economic resources, technological capabilities and political influence (Farny, 2016). Developing countries often find themselves in positions of relative dependence, relying on developed nations for capital, technology, markets, and access to resources (Ikechukwu and Eke, 2013).

The Globalization theory also recognizes that economic globalization presents both opportunities and challenges for developing nations. While it can create avenues for economic growth, technological transfer and access to global

markets, it also poses risks and challenges. Developing countries may face difficulties in competing with established economies, experience vulnerability to global market fluctuations, and encounter challenges related to economic inequality and social disparities (Lascurain, 2016).

In the context of the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy in Uganda, applying Economic Globalization Theory allows for an examination of the power dynamics and economic dependencies involved. It provides a lens to explore how Uganda, as a developing economy, is situated within the global economic system and how the trade war between the United States and China may affect its trade patterns, investment flows, and overall economic well-being. By analyzing the trade war through the framework of Economic Globalization Theory, the dissertation aims to uncover the specific challenges and opportunities faced by Uganda in its economic relations with these global powers.

Literature foundation

Impact of the trade war in Africa

The U.S.-China trade war has been a significant economic event that has drawn attention from various sectors worldwide (Chen et al, 2020). The trade war started in 2018, with both countries imposing tariffs on each other's goods (Goulard, 2020). The trade war was fueled by a range of factors, including concerns about intellectual property theft and technology transfer, as well as broader strategic and political considerations (Lin, 2020). The trade war's impacts have been felt by both the U.S.A and Chinese economies, which have experienced slower economic growth, job losses and increased consumer prices (Lau, 2020).

The U.S.-China trade war has had a significant impact on the global economy, leading to increased uncertainty and volatility in the global markets (Cheng et al., 2023). This has affected trade and investment flows and could result in slower economic growth. The trade war has also raised concerns about the potential for protectionism and the breakdown of the rules-based international trading system (Tan and Steinberg, 2022).

Several studies have examined the potential impacts of the U.S.-China trade war on various sectors, including agriculture, manufacturing and technology. For instance, the Peterson Institute for International Economics (2019) conducted a study that found that the trade war had a significant impact on Uganda agriculture, resulting in export losses and lower prices for commodities such as soybeans. Another study by the National Bureau of Economic Research (2020) found that the trade war led to a decline in Uganda manufacturing output and employment.

The technology sector has not been spared from the impacts of the U.S.-China trade war. The trade war has led to concerns about the impact on innovation and global supply chains. The Center for Strategic and International Studies (2019) conducted a study that argued that the trade war could lead to a bifurcation of the global technology industry, with separate systems and standards emerging in the U.S.A and China.

The U.S.-China trade war has far-reaching implications for the global economy, and its impacts will likely continue to be felt for years to come. It is essential to understand the potential impacts of the trade war on various sectors and economies to develop strategies for mitigating the negative effects.

Numerous empirical studies have investigated how the U.S.-China trade war has affected developing economies, including nations in Africa, Asia and Latin America. These studies have concluded that the trade war has had a notable influence on these countries' economies, primarily due to alterations in worldwide commodity prices, decreased foreign investment and a deceleration in global growth.

In 2019, the World Bank conducted a study that analyzed how the trade war had affected Uganda's economy. The study revealed that the trade war had diminished the amount of goods that Uganda exported to China and caused a drop in global commodity prices. As a result, the country saw a decrease in economic growth and an increase in inflation. The study also discovered that foreign investment in Uganda, particularly in the manufacturing sector, had decreased due to the trade war.

The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) conducted another study in 2019 that investigated the broader impact of the trade war on developing nations. The study revealed that the trade war had resulted in a reduction in global trade and an increase in uncertainty, which had contributed to a slowdown in global growth. Moreover, the study discovered that the trade war had caused a shift in global supply chains, with some companies moving their production from China to other countries in the region, such as Vietnam and Bangladesh.

Additionally, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) conducted a third study in 2019 that examined how the trade war affected emerging market and developing economies. The study concluded that the trade war had resulted in a decline in global growth and an increase in uncertainty, which had adversely affected these economies. Furthermore, the study found that the trade war had led to a decrease in global trade, especially in the electronics and automotive industries.

Chong and Li (2019) conducted a study investigating the causes and economic impact of the trade war between China and the U.S.A. They categorized the causes into remote causes and immediate causes. In their analysis, they observed that the imposition of tariffs on Chinese goods by the U.S.A, which led to the trade war, did not start with the Trump administration but can be traced back to 1991. They explained that the USA began investigating China in 1991, focusing on areas such as intellectual property rights, unfair trade barriers and clean energy. Both countries threatened to use tariffs as retaliation. In 2010, the Obama administration initiated an investigation on China's subsidy policies and investment in green technologies under Section 301.

Prior to the official start of the trade war in 2018, President Trump also initiated a national security investigation under Section 232 on steel and aluminum imports. Due to China's significant production in these industries, it was believed that China was the target of this investigation. In 2018, the USA imposed numerous tariffs on imports from China, and tensions escalated when President Trump threatened to impose additional tariffs on Chinese goods. In response, China also announced reciprocal tariffs on imports from the USA to match these threats.

In summary, Chong and Li identified three key factors that contributed to the imposition of tariffs by the USA on Chinese goods: the historical investigation into China's practices, the Section 301 investigation initiated by the Obama administration and the Section 232 investigation conducted by the Trump administration for national security reasons. These factors played a significant role in fueling the trade war between the two countries.

Impact on Uganda's imports and exports

According to Prosper magazine (2021), Dr. Adam Mugume, the executive director of research at the Bank of Uganda, mentioned that the trade conflicts between the United States and China may not have a direct impact on Uganda. However, there are significant indirect consequences to consider. The ongoing trade tensions have the potential to greatly slow down global economic growth, which in turn could hinder Uganda's own economic development.

According to Prosper magazine (2021), Mr. Fred Muhumuza, a development economist and lecturer at Makerere University, stated that the trade dispute between the United States of America and China will indirectly affect Uganda. As China seeks new markets, it is likely to lower its tariffs for exporting goods to countries with low or no tariffs. Consequently, China may flood the Ugandan market with its products at very low prices in an attempt to compensate for the loss of the United States of America market. China's increased focus on markets outside the United States will have a detrimental impact on local Ugandan products and the manufacturing sector, as Uganda may lack the capacity for trade protectionism similar to the USA. Uganda, as a primarily net importer, lacks the ability to implement trade protectionism measures effectively. This is because imposing high tariffs (also known as protectionism) would result in its limited exports being subject to high tariffs in other countries. As a result, Uganda needs to carefully consider alternative strategies to promote economic growth and balance its trade deficit without resorting to protectionist policies.

In terms of exports, the U.S.-China trade war presents some opportunities. According to Ambassador Onen, the current trade tension opens up possibilities for Uganda to capitalize on. One potential strategy is to attract Chinese investors to Uganda and establish textile manufacturing facilities for exporting purposes. By producing textiles within

Uganda, these products can then be exported to the United States under the AGOA arrangement, as they would be recognized as Ugandan goods. The African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA) is an initiative that grants preferential treatment, exempting duties on products originating from selected sub-Saharan African countries (SSAs).

Ambassador Onen further explained that for Ugandan products to meet the requirements of AGOA, they must undergo a value addition process, with a minimum of 35 percent value addition. This threshold is achievable, and it could even be increased to 50 percent if cotton were included in the manufacturing process.

The U.S.-China trade war has had a significant impact on Uganda's imports and exports, as several authors have noted. According to a study by Mugume (2020), the trade war has led to a reduction in Uganda's exports to China, which declined by 46% in 2019. Similarly, Uganda's exports to the U.S. decreased by 33% in the same year, as noted by the International Trade Center (2019). This decrease in exports has had a significant impact on Uganda's foreign exchange earnings, which has affected the country's economy. In addition, the trade war has led to a decrease in Uganda's imports from China and the U.S., which has affected industries that rely on imported goods, such as manufacturing and construction. According to a study by the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (2020), the decrease in imports has led to a decline in Uganda's production capacity and competitiveness. Other authors, such as Atwine (2019) and Ntayi (2020) have noted that the trade war has also affected Uganda's agricultural sector, as China and the U.S. are major buyers of Uganda's agricultural products. Therefore, the U.S.-China trade war has had a significant impact on Uganda's imports and exports, which has affected the country's economy and industries.

Several studies have examined the impact of the US-China trade war on the economies of various countries. For example, Fajgelbaum and Khandelwal (2021) found that the trade war had a negative impact on both the U.S. and Chinese economies, and that the spillover effects were felt by other countries as well. Similarly, a study by Felbermayr et al. (2019) found that the trade war had a negative impact on the global economy, particularly on countries that are heavily integrated into global value chains.

In the case of Uganda, several reports have suggested that the trade war could have a negative impact on the country's economy. For example, a report by the African Development Bank (2019) noted that the trade war could result in a decline in global demand for Ugandan exports, particularly agricultural products such as coffee and tea. Similarly, a research by the International Growth Centre (2019) found that the trade war could lead to a decline in foreign investment in Uganda, as investors become more cautious amid the uncertainty caused by the trade tensions.

Numerous studies have examined the impact of various economic factors on Uganda's GDP growth rate. For example, a study by Abuka et al. (2015) found that changes in global commodity prices, particularly for oil and non-oil commodities, have a significant impact on Uganda's GDP growth rate. Similarly, a study by Kalyango et al. (2016) found that changes in foreign exchange rates have a significant impact on Uganda's trade balance and, consequently, on its GDP growth rate.

In terms of government policies, several studies have examined the impact of various policies on Uganda's economy. For example, a study by Kasirye et al. (2015) found that government spending on infrastructure has a positive impact on Uganda's GDP growth rate. Similarly, a study by Nakabuye and Kikomeko (2018) found that policies aimed at promoting agricultural productivity have a positive impact on Uganda's economy.

Policy implications and mitigation strategies in Africa

The U.S.-China trade war has impacted Africa's economy in numerous ways, including through variations in global commodity prices, reduced foreign investment and a slowdown in global growth (An et al, 2020). Uganda is a significant exporter of agricultural commodities (Blake et al, 2001). Hence, the changes in global commodity prices have had a significant impact on the nation's economy. Reduced foreign investment has also been a significant impact, with investors being more cautious about investing in developing economies due to increased uncertainty (Zhang et al, 2023).

The policy implications of the U.S.-China trade war for developing economies such as Uganda include the need for diversification and the promotion of regional integration. According to (Madyo, 2008), diversification is essential to

reduce dependence on a single market and reduce the impact of fluctuations in global commodity prices. Regional integration can also help mitigate the negative effects of the trade war by promoting intra-regional trade and investment (Nguyen, 2019).

Several mitigation strategies have been proposed for developing economies in the face of the U.S.-China trade war. One such strategy is to increase domestic production and value addition (Fajgelbaum and Khandelwal, 2021). This can be achieved through increased investment in infrastructure, research and development, and technology transfer. Another strategy is to promote trade with other markets, including developing economies, to reduce dependence on the U.S. and China. Promoting trade with other developing economies can also help reduce the impact of global commodity price fluctuations (Annan, 2022).

Uganda's Economic Condition before the trade war

In the years before the trade war, Uganda has experienced positive economic growth and made progress in several key areas. The country has implemented economic reforms aimed at attracting foreign investment and promoting private sector development (Wakyereza, 2017). Riddervold (2011) stated that Uganda was witnessing a steady increase in foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows, particularly in sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing and services.

The agricultural sector plays a significant role in Uganda's economy, employing a large portion of the population and contributing to export earnings (World Bank Group, 2018). The country is known for its agricultural products such as coffee, tea and horticultural produce. Additionally, Uganda has made efforts to diversify its economy by promoting sectors such as tourism, information and communication technology (ICT), and oil exploration (Rauschendorfer et al, 2021).

Despite these positive developments, Uganda faces several challenges in its economic landscape. Poverty and income inequality remain persistent issues, with a significant portion of the population living below the poverty line (World Bank, 2016). The country also faces infrastructure gaps, including inadequate transportation networks and limited access to electricity.

Furthermore, Uganda heavily relies on international trade for economic growth and development. The country exports commodities such as coffee, tea, gold and oilseeds, while importing various manufactured goods, machinery and petroleum products. Uganda's trade partners include countries from both developed and developing regions, with China being an important trading partner in recent years (World Bank, 2013).

In summary, prior to the U.S.-China trade war, Uganda's economy showed positive signs of growth and diversification, with efforts to attract foreign investment and promote sectors such as agriculture and services. However, challenges such as poverty, income inequality, and infrastructure gaps persisted. Uganda's international trade played a significant role in its economy, with China being a notable trading partner. Understanding this pre-trade war economic condition provides important context for assessing the subsequent impact of the trade war on Uganda's economy.

Literature Comment

The available literature review on how the trade war has impacted Uganda's economy made it easier to understand the potential effects of the dispute. Numerous theories offer significant perspectives on the workings of global trade and how it affects domestic economies. Among these theories are the theories of trade diversion and creation, comparative advantage, dependency, political economy, international finance, protectionism, neoclassical and economic globalization.

The review highlights several key findings from previous studies, including reduced exports, declines in global commodity prices, reduced foreign investment, and fluctuations in trade flows, investment flows, prices, and exchange rates. These results indicate that there are several ways in which the trade war might have a major negative influence on Uganda's economy.

This study tries to examine the precise effects of the trade war on Uganda's economic growth concentrating on the

GDP level and building upon the theories covered in the literature review. The study attempts to provide empirical evidence on the degree to which the trade war has affected Uganda's GDP and the dynamics of trade flows with China and the United States by incorporating variables like Uganda-China exports, Uganda-China imports, Uganda-USA exports and Uganda-USA imports.

The utilization of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model to estimate the short- and long-term impacts of the trade war on Uganda's GDP aligns with both international finance and neoclassical theories. It closes a research gap by providing reliable and accurate data that allow for a quantitative examination of how the trade war has affected Uganda's overall economic performance.

Through hypothesis testing and empirical support the study seeks to advance theoretical understanding of the relationships between Uganda's GDP and the economic factors related to the trade war. Together with the analysis of trade investment and exchange rates the study's hypothesis that the trade war harms Uganda's GDP highlights the interdependence of economies and the impact of power dynamics which is highlighted by political economy theories.

This study attempts to close the research gap, provide insightful analysis and policy recommendations in order to lessen the negative effects of the trade war on Uganda's economy. With the use of empirical data and contextual analysis the study seeks to offer specific recommendations for stakeholders and policymakers that take into consideration Uganda's unique circumstances. According to the theories of economic globalization and comparative advantage, this strategy is in line with the goal of resolving the difficulties brought about by the trade war and optimizing economic outcomes.

By providing a comprehensive overview of the theories and previous studies relevant to the effects of the trade war on Uganda's economy, the literature review ends with this analysis. A comprehensive and customized analysis to these theories is provided by the selected policy recommendations and methodology hypothesis. This study fills a research gap and offers insightful information that enhances the body of knowledge and helps policymakers make decisions about how to best navigate the opportunities and challenges presented by the trade war.

The literature review provides a solid foundation for understanding the potential consequences of the U.S.-China trade war on Uganda's economy. In order to formulate the study's goals and methodology, the review skillfully makes use of a number of economic theories. The integration of theories such as Dependency Theory, Comparative Advantage Theory, Trade Diversion and Creation Theory among others demonstrates a thorough understanding of the implications of the trade wars.

International finance and neoclassical theories of finance are in line with the methodology of using the ARDL model to estimate the effects on Uganda's GDP. It makes it possible to conduct a quantitative analysis that can yield useful information about the scope of the trade wars effects and how specifically it has affected Uganda's economic growth.

The objectives of the study's empirical analysis and hypothesis testing are to produce solid evidence and increase theoretical understanding of the connections between Uganda's GDP economic factors and the trade war. This approach demonstrates how to comprehensively address the research objectives and bridge the existing research gap.

Additionally, the research takes a proactive and realistic approach to making policy recommendations meant to lessen the negative effects of trade disputes. Policymakers and stakeholders receive crucial guidance from the study to help them overcome the challenges posed by the trade war and maximize economic outcomes by tailoring the recommendations to Uganda's unique economic circumstances.

All things considered, the goals of the selected methodology and the policy recommendations were strongly supported by the literature review. By incorporating pertinent theories and building upon prior findings, the research

shows promise to substantially contribute to the body of knowledge already available on the effects of the trade war on Uganda's economy.

Research Methodology

This episode seeks to give a comprehensive picture of how this paper was conducted. According to McCombes and George (2023), a research methodology is a specific technique that is applied with the aim of recognizing, selecting, processing and examining information about a specific topic. This section also includes the processes and ways that are used for steering the research study. This chapter contains the research design, research apparatuses, data analysis techniques and data gathering methods. Furthermore, this episode outlines the dependability and rationality of the model applied. In short, in this segment, the investigator will give details on the practical steps applied so as to conduct the research. In addition, the research objectives and questions will be responded to.

The study hypotheses are as follows:

Hypothesis 1: The U.S.-China trade war affects Uganda's gross domestic product growth negatively.

According to Bao et al. (2022), the trade war has an impact in the GDP levels. It is acknowledged that the trade war can impact the output or gross domestic product both positively or negatively

Supporting this perspective, Arosh (2021) highlights that almost all countries are adversely affected by this trade war. As a result of the U.S-China trade war, global trade has diminished massively and almost all the nations were badly effected. The total output of most developing countries was affected.

According to Saeed (2023), the trade war contributed to a rise in import duties between the U.S and China. This conflict has a serious knock-on impact on worldwide trade. The Asian Development Bank reported that China is projected to experience a 0.5% decline of its GDP, whereas the U.S was anticipated to experience a decline of more than 0.05%. Since Uganda hugely imports its machinery and capital goods from China and the U.S, it can be investigated how the Ugandan GDP is affected.

The trade war led to a substantial decrease in trade between America and China and this is supplemented by significant trade diversion on imports from other countries, causing reorganization of value chains. The simulation analysis demonstrated direct impacts of increasing tariffs on the global economy leading to a reduction in GDP globally (Bekkers and Schroeter, 2020).

The intensification of the trade war diminishes GDP in both China and the USA by -1.41percent and -1.35 percent, respectively and this spills over to other nations that heavily relies on the U.S and China (Itakura, 2019).

Hypothesis 2: Deviations in exchange rates, trade flows, prices and investment flows have a significant impact on Uganda's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth.

From a study conducted by Katusiime et al., (2016), the worldwide financial crisis has unsettled capital flows and trade in most emerging economies. This was caused by amplified exchange rate volatility. The results proved that exchange rates negatively influence economic growth in Uganda.

The findings by Musinguzi and Rapha, (2019) on exports to economic growth exposed a strong positive correlation between exports and GDP growth. Conversely, the relationship coefficient of exports and GDP growth was slightly bigger than the correlation between the imports and GDP growth.

The study by Odongo, (2012) discovered that international capital flows have great significance in promoting Ugandan economic growth. Outcomes further exposed that the causes of Foreign Direct Investment inflows are domestic investments, GDP growth, exports and imports growth.

According to Ramos-Herrera and Sosvilla-Rivero(2023), real economic growth can be hampered by departures from the equilibrium exchange rate. Cephas et al., (2017) determines that the growth of trade and GDP has a positive

and statistically significant relationship. Economic growth depends on low inflation, according to Sattarov (2011). Abu et al., (2016) highlights the significance of foreign investment in propelling economic growth.

Research design

In order to investigate the ramifications of the U.S.-China trade war on the Ugandan economy, this research study made use of the quantitative research design. According to Chiinze (2017), quantitative research is viewed as the structured inquiry about an occurrence through the collection of arithmetical data and execution of numerical, mathematical or computational methods. By applying this method, the researcher aimed to derive empirical understandings and numerical evidence concerning the influence of the U.S.-China trade war. With the aim of addressing the research questions, the ARDL model was employed as the primary analytical framework. This provided a vigorous method for investigating the influence of the trade war on Uganda's economic indicators. By engaging this investigative method, the researcher could successfully evaluate the magnitude to which the U.S.-China trade war has influenced numerous parts of Uganda's economy and establish the specific channels through which these effects manifest.

Typically, researchers have traditionally employed two main approaches: the quantitative approach and the qualitative approach (Mohajan, 2018). The third approach, known as the mixed method, involves combining both quantitative and qualitative methods. A qualitative research methodology focuses on exploring qualitative phenomena that involve subjective qualities. It relies on the use of words and reasoning, making it non-numerical in nature. The primary objective of qualitative research is to understand the emotions, meanings and descriptions of a particular situation. In this approach, the researcher heavily relies on observations and detailed descriptions.

According to Eyisi (2016), quantitative research aims to uncover evidence behind situations and is based on measurable assumptions. In this type of research, data is collected using numerical values that can be categorized, ordered and measured. Quantitative techniques allow researchers to conduct extensive surveys with a large number of participants, yielding consistent results. The focus of quantitative research is on testing the significance of hypotheses and answering questions such as the extent of a relationship or its existence. This approach relies on logical analysis and utilizes numerical data. However, quantitative methods are often rigid and provide limited insight into the attitudes and behaviors of the subjects under investigation. In this particular study, quantitative approaches were employed to analyze data obtained from audited financial statements.

Data Collection

The acquisition of data plays a substantial role in the statistical examination of information (Douglas, 2015). Data, which can possess qualitative or quantitative attributes (Daniel, 2016), refers to a compilation of values. In this study, secondary quantitative data was employed, sourced from a variety of secondary outlets such as the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the Uganda Bureau of Statistics and online platforms. This secondary data, previously amassed for alternative intentions, was adaptable for dissimilar objectives (Martins et al., 2018). The data encompasses the timeframe from January 2018 to December 2021, coinciding with the duration of the trade conflict. Effective data collection and organization are crucial for making information available and drawing meaningful conclusions (Douglas, 2015; Ajayi, 2017). Data serves as the raw material from which information is derived, comparable to sorghum for brewing beer (Mesly, 2015). Primary and secondary sources can both be utilized for data collection (Mesly, 2015).

Primary data

According to Mesly (2015), the researcher is typically the initial source of data collection. Primary sources of data encompass methods such as personal interviews, surveys, questionnaires, observations and experiments. Martins (2018) highlights that firsthand data obtained through primary sources tends to be highly valuable as it often provides

transparency and reliability in studying a particular phenomenon. However, it is important to note that primary data collection can be costly, challenging to obtain and has limitations in terms of scope and scale.

Secondary data

Gray (2014) explains that secondary data refers to information that already exists and can be utilized for various research purposes or for record-keeping purposes. This data is obtained by the researcher from sources other than their own data collection efforts, such as data published in scientific journals (Mesly, 2015). Secondary data provides a historical perspective and organizational context to the research. One of the advantages of secondary data is its cost-effectiveness since it relies on data that has already been collected by other parties. In many cases, the cost of purchasing and acquiring secondary data is lower than the expenses associated with collecting fresh data (Gray, 2014). Furthermore, secondary data is considered reliable as it has been collected and published by experts, adding value to the research. Gray (2014) also highlights that secondary data is particularly suitable for academic researchers who need to complete their papers within specified timeframes. Examples of secondary data sources include books, government publications, websites, internal records, journal articles, and other relevant sources.

However, there are instances where secondary data may be outdated, flawed, biased or inaccurate, which can potentially impact the findings of a study. In the present research, secondary data was obtained from books, government publications, websites, internal records, journal articles and others.

Variables

The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) will be used in the research study as the dependent variable. Trade flows encompass the movement of imports and exports between China and the United States, with inflation and currency rates considered as key independent variables in the analysis.

The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is a widely utilized measure for assessing economic activity within a nation, reflecting the aggregate value of domestically generated goods and services and indicating their trajectory over time (Dyanand Sheiner, 2018). In this research investigation, Uganda's GDP will serve as the dependent variable, providing a valuable indicator of the nation's overall economic performance. By employing Uganda's GDP as the dependent variable, the study aims to assess the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the country's economic performance.

In terms of independent variables, the study considers trade flows, exchange rates and inflation. Trade flows encompass both imports and exports between Uganda, the United States, China and are crucial factors that may experience repercussions due to the trade conflict. These changes in trade flows can significantly influence a nation's economy by impacting export and import levels, as well as the trade balance (Blavasciunaite et al., 2020). The ongoing trade tensions between the U.S. and China have the potential to impact Uganda's economic performance, making these variables significant factors to analyze. The trade dynamics between Uganda, the U.S. and China may be affected by the trade conflict, which involves the imposition of tariffs and trade barriers by these influential nations. Consequently, changes in trade flows can exert a substantial influence on the broader economic landscape, affecting export and import levels as well as the trade balance.

Exchange rates are crucial factors to consider as they contribute to the cost implications associated with traded goods and services. They possess the capacity to exert a notable influence on trade flows and overall economic dynamics (Auboin et al., 2011). Fluctuations in exchange rates can have significant effects on trade flows and the broader economic landscape, making them essential variables to analyze in this study. Exchange rates play a vital role in determining the cost implications of traded goods and services, and their fluctuations can impact trade flows and overall economic dynamics.

Inflation is a metric that gauges the pace at which overall price levels undergo upward adjustments over time. It holds the potential to sway economic activities by exerting influence over consumer expenditure, business investments, and other economic choices (Coibion et al., 2020). Including inflation as an independent variable enables an analysis of its potential impact on Uganda's economy during the U.S.-China trade war. Inflation measures the rate at which overall

price levels change over time and can significantly influence economic activities, such as consumer expenditure, business investments and other economic choices.

This research aims to estimate the impact of the U.S.-China trade conflict on Uganda’s economy by incorporating relevant variables into a regression framework. It also considers other factors that may affect GDP. The model enables the identification of specific channels through which the trade war affects the economy, such as changes in trade flows or exchange rates.

While we understand the importance of other essential elements such as population, natural resources, education, technology, political environment, and globalization in analyzing a country's economy, for the specific focus of this study on the impact of the U.S.-China trade war, the researcher chose variables that are directly related to the trade war and its consequences on Uganda.

The researcher will further justify and support the chosen variables by providing empirical evidence, theoretical frameworks and relevant literature in the dissertation. This will ensure that the selected variables align with the research topic and contribute to a comprehensive analysis of the U.S.-China trade war’s impact on Uganda's economy.

Data sources

For this study, Ugandan GDP was obtained from www.macrotrends.com. The data for the trade flows (Uganda-China exports and imports, Uganda-U.S.A exports and imports) was obtained from tradingeconomics.com. Data on Uganda exchange rate and inflation was attained from the www.investing.com website.

Symbol	Measurement	Type	Variable	Definition
GDP	In Uganda, GDP was measured in United States dollars (\$).	Dependent Variable	Gross Domestic Product	GDP measures the total value of goods and services produced within Uganda’s borders.
UCHEXPO	Uganda-China exports were measured in United States dollars (\$).	Independent Variable	Uganda-China exports	Uganda-China exports refer to the goods that were shipped from Uganda to China
UCHIMPO	Uganda-China exports were measured in United States dollars (\$).	Independent Variable	Uganda-China imports	Uganda-China exports refer to the goods that were shipped from China to Uganda.
USEXPO	Uganda-USA exports were measured in United States dollars (\$).	Independent Variable	Uganda-USA exports	Uganda-USA exports refer to the goods that were shipped from Uganda to USA
USIMPO	Uganda-USA imports were measured in United States dollars (\$).	Independent Variable	Uganda-USA imports	Uganda-USA exports refer to the goods that were shipped from USA to Uganda.
EXRATE	This was expressed as the amount of Ugandan shillings required to purchase one United States dollar.	Independent Variable	Exchange rate	This is the rate at which the Ugandan shilling is exchanged for the United States dollar.
CPI	It was utilized by the consumer price index (CPI).	Independent Variable		

Variable measurements

Source: Author (2022)

Diagnostic tests

Various diagnostic tests were conducted before the ARDL Model. These tests were conducted to assess if the assumptions of the model are satisfied. This was done to ensure the validity of the model and reliable inference. According to Ernst and Albers (2017), diagnostic tests aid in identifying potential issues such as violations of assumptions, outliers, or influential observations. Furthermore, these tests also guide the model improvement and refinement. This allows researchers to make necessary adjustments. Additionally, these tests facilitate model comparison, helping select the most appropriate model for the research question. Overall, diagnostic tests ensure the reliability, validity and appropriateness of statistical models, leading to more robust and accurate analysis. In this research, multicollinearity, serial autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity tests were carried out for diagnostic testing. In order to run the ARDL model, there should be an optimal lag for both the dependent and the independent variables and the error term should not be auto correlated.

Multicollinearity

Multicollinearity refers to high correlations among independent variables in a regression model, leading to skewed or misleading results. It can cause wider confidence intervals and less reliable probabilities for the effects of independent variables. In this research, the correlation matrix is used to test for multicollinearity between the dependent variables.

According to Elith et al. (2012), when the absolute value of a correlation coefficient exceeds 0.7, it generally signifies a strong correlation between predictor variables. In the context of the paper, correlations that fall within this range, meaning those greater than 0.7 or less than -0.7, will be removed or disregarded.

Serial correlation

Serial correlation, also known as autocorrelation occurs when the errors or residuals in a time series data are correlated across different time periods. This means that the error in one period is related to the error in a subsequent period. It can give rise to several issues, including:

Inefficient estimation using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and any forecasts based on those estimates. Inefficient estimators provide less information about a sample, requiring larger sample sizes to achieve reliable results.

Overestimation of goodness of fit in the case of a time series with positive serial correlation and an independent variable that increases over time.

Underestimation of standard errors for a time series with positive serial correlation and an independent variable that grows over time.

Inflated T-statistics, which can lead to misleading interpretations of the statistical significance of regression coefficients.

False positives for significant regression coefficients, implying that a regression coefficient appears to be statistically significant when it is actually not.

This serial correlation or autocorrelation introduces dependencies between errors in a time series, which can impact the accuracy and reliability of statistical estimation and inference. In this paper, the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test will be used to test for serial correlation.

The Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test is a statistical test used to examine the presence of serial correlation in a regression model. The test evaluates whether the residuals of the model exhibit significant serial correlation. It is guided by the following hypothesis:

H_0 : There is no serial correlation.

H_1 : There is presence of serial correlation.

If the p-value is below 0.05, serial correlation is deemed significant. If the p-value is above 0.05, there is insufficient evidence to conclude the presence of serial correlation.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity occurs when the variability of the residuals, or error terms are not consistent across different values of the independent variable in a regression analysis. This leads to an uneven spread or scatter of the residuals. Hypothesis for testing for heteroscedasticity are:

H_0 : There is no heteroscedasticity in the residuals of the regression model, meaning the variance of the residuals is constant. Where $p > 0.05$.

H_1 : There is heteroscedasticity in the residuals of the regression model, meaning the variance of the residuals is not constant. Where $p < 0.05$.

After performing the diagnostic tests, the researcher proceeded to conduct descriptive statistics.

Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics involve summarizing and describing the main characteristics and features of the data set. This step helps in gaining a better understanding of the data, exploring its distribution, central tendency, variability and other important characteristics.

Normality Distribution

According to Orchan (2020), the assumption of normality is necessary to determine whether a parametric or non-parametric test should be used. Various methods, including assessing skewness and kurtosis, are proposed in the literature to test for normality. Normality tests are employed to assess whether a dataset can be adequately modeled by a normal distribution and to determine the likelihood of the underlying random variable being normally distributed.

According to Curran-Everett and Benos (2004), statistical errors are common in scientific literature, with approximately half of published papers containing at least one error. Many parametric statistical measures, such as t-tests, correlation, regression and analysis of variance, assume that the collected data follows a normal distribution (Ghasemi and Zahediasl, 2012). This assumption implies that the populations from which the samples are taken are normally distributed (Driscoll, Lecky, and Crosby, 2000). The assumption of normality is particularly crucial when establishing reference intervals for variables (Royston, 1991). Royston further emphasizes that normality assumptions must be taken seriously, as deviations from these assumptions can lead to incorrect statistical inferences.

Testing for normality is essential for various statistical techniques, particularly parametric tests, as their validity relies on this assumption. The purpose of this discussion is to provide an overview of normality testing in statistical analysis and draw reliable conclusions about reality (Field, 2007). Razali and Wah(2011) state that there are several methods available for testing normality, including the Shapiro-Wilk test and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test.

Stationarity test

The gathered data will undergo a test to determine its stationarity. According to Jain and Chetty (2020), stationarity, as examined in the stationery test, refers to a characteristic of a time series where the values of variables do not change with time. Baum (2009) further emphasized that when working with time series data, it is crucial to consider two important aspects: stability and stationarity. Stationarity specifically pertains to individual time series, indicating whether the series has one or more unit roots or exhibits covariance stationarity. On the other hand, the property of stationarity discusses the correlation between two or more variables in a bivariate or multivariate context.

Therefore, ensuring that the data is stationary ensures that the analysis is conducted in a purely unbiased manner. By achieving stationarity, one can accurately determine the nature of variables, make precise projections and predictions, and obtain reliable information about the true relationship between the variables (Jain and Chetty, 2020). It is crucial for the data to be free from the effects of seasonality and trends in order to achieve these goals.

Several tests are available to examine stationarity, such as the Dicky Fuller (DF) Test, Augmented Dicky Fuller (ADF) Test, Philips-Perron (PP) test, Dicky-Fuller- GLS (ERS), Kwiatkowski, Philips, Schmidt, and Shin (KPSS)-Test, among others (Jain and Chetty, 2020).

Dickey-Fuller (DF) Test

The Dickey-Fuller (DF) test is a statistical test used to determine whether a time series has a unit root, which indicates non-stationarity. The test is based on the null hypothesis that the time series has a unit root. This means that it is non-stationary. If the test rejects the null hypothesis, it suggests that the time series is stationary. This indicates that it does not have a unit root. The DF test is widely used in econometrics and time series analysis.

The Dickey-Fuller (DF) test is based on the following regression equation:

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha + \beta y_{t-1} + \gamma_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Where y_t Represents the first difference of the time series variable y_t , y_{t-1} represents the lagged value of the time series variable, α is the intercept term, β is the coefficient on the lagged variable, γ_t represents the deterministic trend term and ε_t is the error term.

The null and alternative hypotheses for the DF test are as follows. Null Hypothesis (H_0). The time series variable y_t has a unit root and is non-stationary. In other words, $\beta = 0$. The alternative Hypothesis (H_a), the time series variable y_t is stationary and does not have a unit root. In other words, $\beta < 0$.

The DF test calculates a test statistic, typically denoted as DF, which is used to compare against critical values to make inferences about the stationarity of the time series. The test statistic is computed based on the estimated coefficient β and the standard error of this coefficient. If the test statistic is greater (less negative) than the critical value, the null hypothesis of a unit root is not rejected, suggesting the time series is non-stationary. However, if the test statistic is smaller (more negative) than the critical value, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating evidence of stationarity in the time series.

The advantages of the Dickey-Fuller (DF) test are that it is simple and it is a widely used test for unit root analysis. It provides critical values to compare test statistics and make inferences. It allows for the inclusion of deterministic trends in the model. Lastly, it can be applied to both univariate and multivariate time series.

The disadvantages of the Dickey-Fuller (DF) test are that it assumes no serial correlation or heteroscedasticity in the data. It has limited power to detect unit roots in small samples. And lastly it does not account for structural breaks in the time series.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is an extension of the DF test that includes additional lagged terms of the dependent variable in the model. The ADF test allows for the presence of autocorrelation and more complex dynamics in the time series. It is commonly used to test for unit roots in time series data and determine the stationarity of the series. The ADF test is particularly useful when dealing with time series that may exhibit serial correlation or other forms of non-stationarity.

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test extends the Dickey-Fuller (DF) test by including additional lagged terms in the model. The ADF test is based on the following regression equation:

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha + \beta y_{t-1} + \sum (\delta_i * \Delta y_{t-i}) + \gamma_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Where Δy_t Represents the first difference of the time series variable y_t , y_{t-1} represents the lagged value of the time series variable, Δy_{t-i} represents the lagged first differences of the time series variable, α is the intercept term, β is the coefficient on the lagged variable, δ_i represents the coefficients on the lagged first differences, γ_t represents the deterministic trend term and ε_t is the error term.

The ADF test allows for the inclusion of lagged differences in the model, capturing more complex dynamics and higher-order autoregressive processes. By including lagged first differences, it accounts for serial correlation and

improves the accuracy of the unit root analysis.

The null and alternative hypotheses for the ADF test are as follows. Null Hypothesis (H_0), the time series variable y_t has a unit root and is non-stationary. In other words, $\beta = 0$. Alternative Hypothesis (H_a), the time series variable y_t is stationary and does not have a unit root. In other words, $\beta < 0$.

Similar to the DF test, the ADF test calculates a test statistic that is compared against critical values to make inferences about the stationarity of the time series. The test statistic is based on the estimated coefficient β and the standard error of this coefficient. If the test statistic is greater (less negative) than the critical value, the null hypothesis of a unit root is not rejected, suggesting non-stationarity in the time series. Conversely, if the test statistic is smaller (more negative) than the critical value, the null hypothesis is rejected, providing evidence of stationarity in the time series.

The advantages are that it allows for the inclusion of lagged differences in the model, capturing more serial correlation. It can handle a higher-order autoregressive process. It provides critical values for different sample sizes and levels of significance. Lastly, it offers more robustness compared to the DF test.

The disadvantages are that it assumes no structural breaks or heteroscedasticity. It can be sensitive to the choice of lag length. It may yield inconsistent results if applied to a time series with strong seasonal patterns.

Philips-Perron (PP) Test

The Phillips-Perron (PP) test is another test for unit roots and non-stationarity in time series data. It is similar to the ADF test but uses a slightly different approach. The PP test is a non-parametric test that estimates the autoregressive structure of the time series and corrects for any serial correlation. It provides a robust alternative to the ADF test and is widely used in econometrics and financial research.

Its advantages are that it does not require specifying the exact form of autocorrelation in the model. It handles both serial correlation and heteroscedasticity. It provides robustness to the presence of structural breaks. It allows for efficient estimation under different assumptions.

The disadvantages are that it may yield less power in detecting unit roots compared to the ADF test. It requires more computational resources compared to the DF and ADF tests. It can be affected by the choice of lag length.

The Phillips-Perron (PP) test is a non-parametric test for unit roots and non-stationarity in time series data. It is based on the following regression equation:

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha + \beta y_{t-1} + \gamma_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Where, Δy_t represents the first difference of the time series variable y_t , y_{t-1} represents the lagged value of the time series variable, α is the intercept term, β is the coefficient on the lagged variable, γ_t represents the deterministic trend term and ε_t is the error term.

The PP test uses a modified version of the DF test by incorporating a robust estimator of the long-run variance to account for serial correlation and heteroscedasticity. It also includes additional terms to control for higher-order serial correlation.

The null and alternative hypotheses for the PP test are as follows. Null Hypothesis (H_0): The time series variable y_t has a unit root and is non-stationary. In other words, $\beta = 0$. The alternative Hypothesis (H_a): The time series variable y_t is stationary and does not have a unit root. In other words, $\beta < 0$.

Similar to the DF test, the PP test calculates a test statistic that is compared against critical values to make inferences about the stationarity of the time series. The test statistic is based on the estimated coefficient β and the standard error of this coefficient, taking into account the robust estimator of the long-run variance. If the test statistic is greater (less negative) than the critical value, the null hypothesis of a unit root is not rejected, indicating non-stationarity in the time series. Conversely, if the test statistic is smaller (more negative) than the critical value, the null hypothesis is rejected, providing evidence of stationarity in the time series.

Dickey-Fuller-GLS (ERS)

The Dickey-Fuller-GLS (ERS) test is an extension of the DF test that incorporates Generalized Least Squares (GLS) estimation. GLS is used to account for heteroscedasticity (unequal variances) and serial correlation in the time series data. The Dickey-Fuller-GLS test is more robust in the presence of such issues and provides more reliable results compared to the standard DF test.

The advantages of Dickey-Fuller-GLS (ERS) test are that it provides more robust results in the presence of heteroscedasticity and serial correlation. It offers efficient estimation of the unit root coefficient. It allows for consistent inference under different assumptions.

The disadvantages of Dickey-Fuller-GLS (ERS) test are that it requires estimating additional parameters, increasing computational complexity. It may still be sensitive to model specification and choice of lag length. It assumes no structural breaks in the time series.

Kwiatkowski, Phillips, Schmidt, and Shin (KPSS) Test

The Kwiatkowski, Phillips, Schmidt, and Shin (KPSS) test is used to test for stationarity in time series data. Unlike the DF and ADF tests, which test for the presence of a unit root, the KPSS test examines the null hypothesis of stationarity. The test assesses whether a time series is trend-stationary or difference-stationary. If the test rejects the null hypothesis, it suggests that the time series is non-stationary.

The Kwiatkowski, Phillips, Schmidt, and Shin (KPSS) test is used to test for stationarity in time series data. Unlike the Dickey-Fuller (DF) and Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) tests that test for the presence of a unit root, the KPSS test examines the null hypothesis of stationarity.

The KPSS test is based on the following regression equation:

$$y_t = \mu_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Where, y_t represents the time series variable, μ_t is the deterministic trend component and ε_t is the error term.

The KPSS test involves two versions: the level form (KPSS level) and the trend form (KPSS trend). The null and alternative hypotheses for the KPSS test are as follows.

KPSS Level. Null Hypothesis (H_0), the time series variable y_t is stationary (has constant mean and variance). The alternative Hypothesis (H_a), the time series variable y_t is non-stationary.

KPSS Trend. Null Hypothesis (H_0): The time series variable y_t is stationary around a deterministic trend. The alternative Hypothesis (H_a): The time series variable y_t is non-stationary with a trend.

The KPSS test calculates a test statistic, typically denoted as KPSS, which is compared against critical values to make inferences about the stationarity of the time series. The test statistic is based on the sum of squared residuals from the regression and the estimated variance of the error term. If the test statistic is greater than the critical value, the null hypothesis of stationarity is rejected, indicating evidence of non-stationarity in the time series. On the other hand, if the test statistic is smaller than the critical value, the null hypothesis is not rejected, suggesting the time series is stationary.

The advantages of the KPSS test include that it tests the null hypothesis of stationarity, which is useful when non-stationarity is not of interest. It provides critical values for different sample sizes and significance levels. It allows for the inclusion of deterministic trends in the model. It offers robustness to structural breaks.

The disadvantages of the KPSS test include that it is less suitable for testing the presence of unit roots. It can yield inconsistent results if applied to time series with strong trend or seasonality. It assumes homoscedasticity and no serial correlation.

In this analysis, the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test was utilized. In this research, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test was selected due to the following reasons:

It incorporates Lagged Terms. The ADF test includes lagged terms of the dependent variable in the model. This

allows for the presence of autocorrelation and more complex dynamics in the time series. By including lagged differences, the ADF test can capture serial correlation and improve the accuracy of the unit root analysis.

Secondly, it handles higher-order processes. The ADF test can handle higher-order autoregressive processes. This was useful since the time series data had longer memory and had more complex dependencies.

Thirdly, the ADF test is known for its robustness as compared to the simpler tests like the Dickey-Fuller (DF) test. Therefore, it provides more reliable results, especially in the presence of serial correlation and heteroscedasticity.

Fourthly, the ADF test provides critical values for different sample sizes and levels of significance. These critical values are essential for comparing the test statistic and to determine whether the null hypothesis of a unit root can be rejected.

Fifthly, the ADF test is widely used in econometrics and time series analysis. It has become a standard tool for testing unit roots and determining the stationarity of time series data. Its widespread usage means that there is a significant body of research and literature available for reference and comparison.

Sixthly, it has extensive software support. Many statistical software packages like Eviews provide built-in functions and routines for conducting the ADF test. This made it easily accessible and convenient for the research.

Lastly, the ADF test results are relatively easy to interpret. The test statistic is compared to critical values, and if the test statistic is lower than the critical value, the null hypothesis of a unit root is rejected, indicating that the time series is stationary.

The Model

For the analysis of the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy in Uganda, the ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) model was utilized. The ARDL model is suitable for examining the relationship between variables with both short-term and long-term dynamics, making it an appropriate choice for this study. Pesaran et al. (2001) introduced the ARDL bounds test, which is applicable when the series exhibit integration of order 0 ($I(0)$) or 1 ($I(1)$), and in the absence of $I(2)$ regressors. Both short-run and long-run coefficients are estimated simultaneously. The cointegration method is derived from the ARDL model. The ordinary least squares technique is utilized to estimate the ARDL model, which offers unique characteristics when compared to other cointegration methods. The ARDL model allows for the inclusion of variables with different orders of integration, without requiring them to have the same order of integration. The subsequent model was employed to estimate the short-run error correction approach and the long-run equilibrium relationship.

The model will include relevant variables that capture the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on Uganda's economy. These variables included Gross Domestic Product, Uganda-China exports, Uganda-China imports, Uganda-USA exports and Uganda-USA imports. The selection of these variables was guided by the existing literature on the U.S.-China trade war and its potential effects on developing economies.

To determine the optimal lag structure for the ARDL model, various diagnostic tests were conducted. This included the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), the Schwarz Bayesian Criterion (SBC), and the Hannan-Quinn Information Criterion (HQIC). These tests helped to identify the appropriate lag length that minimizes information loss and increases model fit.

In addition to the main variables of interest, the model may include control variables which are Exchange rate and Inflation. These control variables are known to influence Uganda's economy. These control variables can help account for other factors that may impact the dependent variables, ensuring a more accurate estimation of the U.S.-China trade war's impact.

The estimation results were interpreted in light of economic theory and existing empirical evidence. The statistical significance and economic magnitude of the coefficients was assessed to determine the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on Uganda's economy

In the study, the ARDL model was employed, and rigorous model selection procedures were conducted to provide a comprehensive analysis of the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on Uganda's economy, considering both short-term and long-term dynamics.

Cointegrating Equation

The cointegration equation follows the following hypothesis:

H_0 : Absence of a cointegrating equation

H_1 : Presence of a cointegrating equation

When conducting the cointegration test, it is crucial to apply it to either the base series or the transformed log series of the raw data (Yu et al, 2019). Hence, performing the test on the first difference of the series is not appropriate. In this work, the cointegration test is performed at log series.

Bounds cointegration test in Eviews

If the calculated F-statistic exceeds the critical value associated with the upper bound (1), it implies the presence of cointegration and supports the existence of a long-term relationship. In this case, the null hypothesis is rejected, and an estimation of the long-run model, known as the Error Correction Model, is warranted.

On the other hand, if the calculated F-statistic falls below the critical value corresponding to the lower bound (0), it indicates the absence of cointegration, suggesting no long-term relationship. In this scenario, the null hypothesis is not rejected, and if the calculated F-statistic is greater than the critical value for the upper bound (1), it indicates the presence of cointegration and supports the existence of a long-term relationship. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the appropriate model to estimate is the Error Correction Model, which captures the long-run dynamics.

Conversely, if the calculated F-statistic is lower than the critical value for the lower bound (0), it suggests no cointegration and the absence of a long-term relationship. In this case, the null hypothesis is not rejected, and the suitable model to estimate is the Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Model, which focuses on the short-run dynamics.

If the F-statistic falls between the lower bound (0) and the upper bound (1), the test outcome is considered inconclusive, and no clear conclusion regarding cointegration can be drawn.

$$GDP = f(UCHEXPO, UCHIMPO, USEXPO, USIMPO, EXRATE, CPI) \quad (3.1)$$

Where GDP =Gross domestic product, $UCHEXPO$ =Uganda-China exports, $UCHIMPO$ =Uganda-China imports, $USEXPO$ = Uganda-USA exports, $USIMPO$ = Uganda-USA imports, $EXRATE$ = Exchange Rate (compared against the United States Dollar), CPI = Consumer Price Index. The model will be formulated in the following manner:

$$GDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 UCHEXPO_{t-1} + \beta_2 UCHIMPO_{t-1} + \beta_3 USEXPO_{t-1} + \beta_4 USIMPO_{t-1} + \beta_5 EXRATE_{t-1} + \beta_6 CPI_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3.2)$$

The autoregressive distributed lag model (ARDL) conditional error correction for the Ugandan GDP growth is offered underneath:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta\text{GDP} + \beta_0 + \beta_1(\Delta\text{UCHEXPO})_{t-1} + \beta_2(\Delta\text{UCHIMPO})_{t-1} + \beta_3(\Delta\text{USEXPO})_{t-1} + \beta_4(\Delta\text{USIMPO})_{t-1} + \beta_5(\Delta\text{EXRATE})_{t-1} \\
 + \beta_6(\Delta\text{CPI})_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^J \beta_7 \Delta(\text{GDP})_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^J \beta_8 \Delta(\text{UCHEXPO})_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^J \beta_9 \Delta(\text{USEXPO})_{t-1} \\
 + \sum_{i=1}^J \beta_{10} \Delta(\text{USIMPO})_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^J \beta_{11} \Delta(\text{EXRATE})_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^J \beta_{12} \Delta(\text{CPI})_{t-1} \\
 + \varepsilon_t \tag{3.3}
 \end{aligned}$$

The ARDL model equation above is a regression model that examines the relationship between the change in GDP (ΔGDP) and various lagged variables. Where β_0 represents the intercept term, which captures the constant effect on GDP that is not related to any of the lagged variables, β_1 to β_6 are coefficients associated with the lagged variables $\Delta\text{UCHEXPO}$, $\Delta\text{UCHIMPO}$, ΔUSEXPO , ΔUSIMPO , ΔEXRATE , and ΔCPI , respectively. These coefficients represent the impact of one unit change in each respective lagged variable on the change in GDP, holding other factors constant, the summations from β_7 to β_{12} capture the effects of multiple lagged periods for GDP, UCHEXPO, USEXPO, USIMPO, EXRATE, and CPI, respectively. These coefficients represent the combined impact of lagged changes in these variables on the current change in GDP and ε_t represents the error term, which accounts for the unexplained variation in the model and includes other factors that might influence the change in GDP but are not explicitly included in the equation.

Wald Coefficient test

The wald test is performed to find out if explanatory variables in a model are significant or not. If a variable is significant, then it adds value to the model. If they are not significant then they must be removed. This is commonly used for diagnostic coefficients testing.

The Wald test, also known as the Wald Chi-Squared Test, is a statistical tool used to determine the overall significance of a group of independent variables in a model. It assesses whether the set of independent variables collectively has a significant impact on the dependent variable. Additionally, the Wald test is employed to examine the individual significance of each independent variable in the model, determining whether each variable makes a significant contribution to the model’s prediction.

H_0 : Coefficient = 0

H_1 : Coefficients \neq 0

Decision criteria. Reject null hypothesis if the prob-value of the F-statistic is ≤ 0.05 .

Robustness Tests

To ensure the reliability and robustness of the findings, several robustness tests will be conducted as part of the methodology for analyzing the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy in Uganda using the ARDL model. These tests aimed to examine the stability of the results and address potential concerns regarding the choice of variables, model specifications, and data sources. The Alternative Lag Structures and Additional Control Variables robustness tests were employed.

Alternative Lag Structures robustness test involves exploring alternative lag structures for the ARDL model. Different lag specifications will be tested to assess whether the selected lag length significantly affects the estimated coefficients and the overall model fit. This test will help determine the sensitivity of the results to the lag structure chosen initially.

Secondly, Additional Control Variables robustness test was conducted in order to account for potential confounding factors. Additional control variables was included in the model. These variables will capture other economic factors that influence Uganda’s economy during the U.S.-China trade war. By including these control

variables, the robustness of the results will be examined to determine whether the estimated impact of the trade war remains consistent.

Research instruments

The study employed quantitative data analysis by utilizing secondary data sources, including trade statistics, economic indicators, exchange rates and pertinent datasets. Through this analysis, trends, correlations and patterns were identified, shedding light on the trade wars influence on Uganda's economy. Furthermore, economic models were employed to simulate and project the potential economic ramifications of the trade war on Uganda, estimating alterations in trade flows, GDP growth, inflation rates and other significant macroeconomic factors.

Validity and Reliability

Ensuring the validity and reliability of the research topic "The impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy in Uganda" utilizing the ARDL Model is crucial. Validity is addressed by carefully selecting variables that accurately represent the concept of interest and employing robust research design. Internal validity is maintained by controlling for confounding factors and employing appropriate statistical techniques. External validity is considered by ensuring the generalizability of findings beyond Uganda. Reliability is ensured through the use of reliable data sources and conducting sensitivity analyses to assess model stability. Transparent reporting and peer review further enhance the overall validity and reliability of the study.

Ethical considerations

Ethical considerations were applied on secondary data sources. Data sources were appropriately cited. Limitations in the data were acknowledged and addressed transparently. The use of secondary data followed legal and ethical guidelines, ensuring compliance with copyright and intellectual property rights.

The researcher maintained objectivity and minimized potential bias throughout the research process. Any personal or professional biases that could influence the research findings were recognized and addressed. The research design and analysis were conducted in a transparent and unbiased manner to ensure the integrity and validity of the results.

Chapter summary

The methodology chapter of this study focused on outlining the methods employed to achieve the research objectives. These methods were carefully selected to ensure the reliability and validity of the findings. By employing rigorous and appropriate techniques, the study aimed to provide robust insights into the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy in Uganda.

The ARDL model was introduced as the primary analytical framework. The ARDL model was chosen due to its ability to capture both short-term and long-term dynamics and account for potential endogeneity and non-stationarity issues. The use of the ARDL model allowed for a comprehensive analysis of the relationship between the U.S.-China trade war and Uganda's economy.

Furthermore, the chapter emphasized the importance of conducting model selection procedures to choose the appropriate lag length and control variables. Various robustness tests were employed to ensure the reliability of the results. These tests included assessing the stability of parameter estimates, sensitivity to lag length, inclusion of additional control variables, utilization of alternative data sources and conducting subsample analysis.

By employing these robustness tests, the study aimed to address potential concerns and enhance the credibility of the findings. The chapter highlighted the significance of these tests in evaluating the stability, consistency, and generalizability of the estimated effects. Additionally, the chapter stressed the importance of sensitivity analysis to examine the impact of deviations from model assumptions.

Overall, the methodology chapter served as a comprehensive guide to the methods used in this study. By employing carefully selected techniques and performing robustness tests, the research aimed to provide reliable and

valid insights into the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on Uganda’s economy. These methods were instrumental in accomplishing the research objectives and added rigor to the study’s findings.

Empirical Analysis

The empirical findings obtained in this study are presented in this chapter, following the methodology described earlier and guided by the literature review presented in Chapter Two. The interpretation of these results is compared to the research questions and objectives outlined in the first chapter. During the estimation of the ARDL model, several procedural tests were conducted by the study to assess various aspects such as stationarity, integration, autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity, normality, and model specification. The results of these tests were determined and documented.

Descriptive Statistics

	GDP	UCHEXPO	UCHIIMPO	UUSEXPO	UUSIMPO	UEXRT	INFLATION
Mean	0.039801	1277803.	38748242	3411895.	4679086.	3685.735	0.003034
Median	0.038750	1335696.	38940552	2852784.	4851996.	3695.000	0.002390
Maximum	0.053656	1354524.	44447736	5933760.	5467392.	3877.140	0.006000
Minimum	0.024594	1059060.	33534252	2350980.	3838080.	3500.640	0.001837
Std. Dev.	0.011873	111603.0	3951884.	1299538.	550062.5	90.94349	0.001526
Skewness	0.012713	-1.415739	0.087058	1.341376	-0.150578	-0.226837	1.355469
Kurtosis	1.332084	3.131002	1.651852	3.047364	2.027543	2.426092	3.059108
Jarque-Bera	6.956478	20.08607	4.619545	17.99850	2.590922	1.337979	18.38169
Probability	0.030862	0.000043	0.099284	0.000124	0.273772	0.512226	0.000102
Sum	2.388050	76668192	2.32E+09	2.05E+08	2.81E+08	221144.1	0.182015
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.008317	7.35E+11	9.21E+14	9.96E+13	1.79E+13	487972.4	0.000137
Observations	60	60	60	60	60	60	60

Measures of central tendency

Mean: The mean represents the average value of the data. For the given variables. The GDP growth has a mean of approximately 0.039801%. Uganda China Exports has a mean of approximately \$1,277,803. Uganda China Imports have a mean of approximately \$38,748,242. Uganda USA Exports have a mean of approximately \$3,411,895. Uganda USA Imports have a mean of approximately \$4,679,086. Uganda exchange rate has a mean of approximately 3,685.735 shillings as compared to 1 United States dollars. Uganda inflation has a mean of approximately 0.003034%.

Maximum: The maximum represents the highest value observed in the data. For the given variables, these are the

maximum values. GDP growth maximum is 0.053656%. Maximum exports between Uganda and China are \$1,354,524. Maximum imports between Uganda and China are \$44,447,736. Maximum exports between Uganda and USA are \$5,933,760. Maximum imports between Uganda and USA are \$5,467,392. The maximum exchange rate of Uganda exchange is 3,877.140 shillings as compared to 1 United States dollars. The maximum inflation rate of Uganda was 0.006000%.

Minimum: The minimum represents the lowest value observed in the data. For the given variables, these are the minimum values. GDP growth 0.024594. Uganda China Exports \$1,059,060. Uganda China Imports \$33,534,252. Uganda USA Exports \$2,350,980. Uganda USA Imports \$3,838,080. Uganda Exchange rate 1:3,500.640. Inflation 0.001837%.

Measures of dispersion: The standard Deviation measures the average amount of deviation or dispersion of the data points from the mean. For the given variables, GDP growth, the standard deviation is approximately 0.011873. Uganda China Exports, the standard deviation is approximately 111,603.0. Uganda China Imports, the standard deviation is approximately 3,951,884. Uganda USA Exports, the standard deviation is approximately 1,299,538. Uganda USA Imports, the standard deviation is approximately 550,062.5. Uganda Exchange Rate, the standard deviation is approximately 90.94349. Inflation, the standard deviation is approximately 0.001526.

Measures of Normality

Skewness

Skewness measures the asymmetry of the data distribution. Positive skewness indicates a longer or fatter tail on the right side of the distribution, while negative skewness indicates a longer or fatter tail on the left side. For the given variables, GDP growth, the skewness is approximately 0.012713, indicating a slightly right-skewed distribution. Uganda China Exports, the skewness is approximately -1.415739, indicating a significantly left-skewed distribution. Uganda China Imports, the skewness is approximately 0.087058, indicating a slightly right-skewed distribution. Uganda USA Exports, the skewness is approximately 1.341376, indicating a significantly right-skewed distribution. Uganda USA Imports, the skewness is approximately -0.150578, indicating a slightly left-skewed distribution. Uganda Exchange Rate, the skewness is approximately -0.226837, indicating a slightly left-skewed distribution. Inflation, the skewness is approximately 1.355469, indicating a significantly right-skewed distribution.

Kurtosis

Kurtosis measures the peakedness or flatness of the data distribution compared to a normal distribution. A positive value indicates a relatively peaked distribution (leptokurtic), while a negative value indicates a relatively flat distribution (platykurtic). For the given variables, GDP growth, the kurtosis is approximately 1.332, indicating a slightly leptokurtic distribution. Uganda China Exports, the kurtosis is approximately 3.131, indicating a leptokurtic distribution. Uganda China Imports, the kurtosis is approximately 1.652, indicating a slightly leptokurtic distribution. Uganda USA Exports, the kurtosis is approximately 3.047, indicating a leptokurtic distribution. Uganda USA Imports, the kurtosis is approximately 2.027543, indicating a leptokurtic distribution. Uganda Exchange Rate, the kurtosis is approximately 2.426092, indicating a leptokurtic distribution. Inflation, the kurtosis is approximately 3.059108, indicating a leptokurtic distribution.

Jarque-Bera Probability Statistics

Jarque-Bera: The Jarque-Bera test is a statistical test to assess if the data follows a normal distribution. It compares the skewness and kurtosis of the data to the expected values for a normal distribution.

H_0 Distribution is normal.

H_1 Distribution is not normal.

Thumb rule

$p < 0.05$ Reject null hypothesis.

GDP growth has a Jarque-Bera statistic of 6.956478, Probability of 0.030862. Since the p-value (0.030862) is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the data for GDP growth does not follow a normal distribution.

Uganda China Exports has a Jarque-Bera statistic of 20.08607. Probability of 0.000043. Since the p-value (0.000043) is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis. The data for Uganda-China exports does not follow a normal distribution.

Uganda China Imports has a Jarque-Bera statistic of 4.619545. Probability of 0.099284. Since the p-value (0.099284) is greater than 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. The data for Uganda-China imports can be considered approximately normal.

Uganda USA Exports has a Jarque-Bera statistic of 17.99850. Probability of 0.000124. Since the p-value (0.000124) is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis. The data for Uganda-USA exports does not follow a normal distribution.

Uganda USA Imports has a Jarque-Bera statistic of 2.590922. Probability of 0.273772. Since the p-value (0.273772) is greater than 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. The data for Uganda-USA imports can be considered approximately normal.

Uganda Exchange Rate has a Jarque-Bera statistic of 1.337979. Probability of 0.512226. Since the p-value (0.512226) is greater than 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. The data for Uganda's exchange rate can be considered approximately normal.

Inflation has a Jarque-Bera statistic of 18.38169. Probability of 0.000102. Since the p-value (0.000102) is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis. The data for inflation does not follow a normal distribution.

Correlation Matrix

	GDP	UCHEXPO	UCHIIMPO	UUSEXPO	UUSIMPO	UEXRT	INFLATION
GDP	1	-0.493	0.037	-0.193	-0.534	0.260	-0.072
UCHEXPO	-0.493	1	-0.160	0.438	0.568	-0.303	0.272
UCHIIMPO	0.037	-0.160	1	-0.479	-0.327	0.413	-0.228
UUSEXPO	-0.193	0.438	-0.479	1	0.639	-0.004	0.548
UUSIMPO	-0.534	0.568	-0.327	0.639	1	-0.168	0.623
UEXRT	0.260	-0.303	0.413	-0.004	-0.168	1	0.189
INFLATION	-0.072	0.272	-0.228	0.648	0.623	0.189	1

The researcher examined the correlation coefficients by looking for high absolute values of correlation coefficients between pairs of predictor variables. In the correlation matrix, there were no correlation coefficients that exceed 0.7 or -0.7. This suggests that there are no strong linear relationships between the variables and there is no multicollinearity.

Serial correlation

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test

F-statistic	0.623	Prob. F(2,251)	0.537
Obs*R-squared	1.293	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.524

Based on the provided information, the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test does not provide strong evidence of serial correlation in the regression model. This is indicated by the relatively high p-values for both the F-statistic and the chi-square test statistic.

A high p-value suggests that the observed test statistics are likely to occur by chance under the null hypothesis of

no serial correlation. The values are greater than 0.05 so we accept H_0 . Therefore, there is no significant evidence of serial correlation in the model based on these test results.

Heterodaskacity

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	0.759	Prob. F(8,253)	0.639
Obs*R-squared	6.144	Prob. Chi-Square(8)	0.631
Scaled explained SS	123.838	Prob. Chi-Square(8)	0.000

The Heteroskedasticity Test, specifically the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test, was conducted on a regression model. The test results indicate that there is no significant evidence of heteroskedasticity in the model. This conclusion is supported by the relatively high p-values associated with the F-statistic and the chi-square test statistics, suggesting that the observed test statistics are likely to occur by chance under the null hypothesis of no heteroskedasticity. Therefore, the model does not exhibit significant heteroskedasticity based on these test results.

Unit root test

Before estimating the model, the researcher conducted unit root tests. The Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test was used to identify the presence of a unit root and to avoid any spurious regression. The results of the ADF stationarity tests indicate that all variables exhibit stationarity at different orders, namely I(0) and I(0). As a result, the null hypothesis of non-stationarity is rejected, leading to the conclusion that the data is stationary at their respective levels. This finding allows for the use of a robust model estimation approach.

Previous studies conducted on similar topics have consistently shown that most macroeconomic variables are non-stationary at their levels but become stationary when differenced once (I(1)). This is because economies undergo evolution and growth over time, and it is widely recognized that economic and financial series often violate the assumption of having a constant mean and variance over time. Having a stationary time series, in this context, would be considered an exception.

Variable	ADF Statistics	Critical Values	p-value	Order of Intergration
GDP	-8.867872	1% - 3.456302	0.0000	I(1)
		5% - 2.872857		
		10% - 2.572875		
UCHIMPO	-16.20150	1% - 3.548208	0.0000	I(1)

		5%	-		
		2.912631			
		10%	-		
		2.594027			
UCHEXPO	-7.816304	1%	-	0.0000	I (1)
		3.455193			
		5%	-		
		2.872370			
		10%	-		
		2.572615			
USIMPORTS	-7.963917	1%	-	0.0000	I(1)
		3.548208			
		5%	-		
		2.912631			
		10%	-		
		2.594027			
USEXPO	7.758024	1%	-	0.0000	I(1)
		3.548208			
		5%	-		
		2.912631			
		10%	-		
		2.594027			
EXRATE	-8.757932	1%	-	0.000	I(0)
		3.548208			
		5%	-		
		2.912631			
		10%	-		
		2.594027			
CPI	-7.567044	1%	-	0.000	I(1)

		3.548208		
	5%	-		
		2.912631		
	10%	-		
		2.594027		

The stationarity test results indicate that the variables, except for Exchange rate, required first differencing (I(1)) to achieve stationarity. Gross Domestic Product, Uganda China Imports, Uganda China Exports, Uganda USA Imports, Uganda USA Exports, and Inflation all show significant ADF statistics with p-values of 0.0000, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis of non-stationarity. These variables achieved stationarity after first differencing. On the other hand, Exchange rate was initially stationary (I(0)), as indicated by its non-significant ADF statistic and p-value of 0.000. These results have important implications for the subsequent modeling and analysis of these variables in the study.

The observed study variables have different orders of integration (I(0) and I(1)) based on the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test results. Conducting a cointegration test is necessary in order to establish the presence of a long-term relationship. However, the Johansen Juselius (1990) cointegration test cannot be applied in this case. This is because it requires all variables to be stationary at the same level or order. Therefore, the appropriate approach is to use the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model bound test (Bekhet, 2012).

The Bounds test, recommended by Pesaran, Shin, and Smith in 2001, is the suitable cointegration test in this scenario. It allows for the examination of both short-run and long-run dynamic correlations, indicating two types of associations.

ARDL Model

Lag selection criteria

To select the appropriate lag for an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, we can consider several criteria, such as the log-likelihood (LogL), likelihood ratio (LR) statistic, final prediction error (FPE), Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Schwarz Information Criterion (SC), and Hannan-Quinn Information Criterion (HQ). Lower values of these criteria indicate better model fit.

Lag length selection for the dependent variable

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-2634.119	NA	46407.23	13.58309	13.59330	13.58714
1	-2393.053	479.6467	13463.77	12.21563*	12.21366*	12.15373*
2	-2376.747	32.35911	12442.37	12.26674	12.29737	12.27888
3	-2374.043	5.353495	12333.52*	12.25795	12.29879	12.27414
4	-2372.183	3.671298	12279.00	12.25352	12.30457	12.27376
5	-2366.437	11.31405*	11982.27	12.22906	12.29031	12.25334
6	-2352.196	27.96885	11191.73	12.26080	12.23227	12.38914
7	-2352.000	0.383452	11238.25	12.26495	12.24662	12.19733

The optimal lag length for the model was determined based on the AIC, which suggests that a lag length of 1 provides the best fit for the dependent variable.

Lag length selection for the independent variables

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-6156.450	NA	42740802	31.76005	31.81109	31.78029
1	-4318.465	3619.125	3734.589	22.41477	22.72103	22.53619
2	-4271.911	90.46836	3342.097	22.01366*	22.66515*	22.52628*
3	-4244.634	52.30456	2603.620*	22.29193	23.10863	22.61574
4	-4201.959	80.72996	3016.833	22.20082	23.27274	22.62582
5	-4167.144	64.96370	2869.369	22.15023	23.47737	22.67642
6	-4132.084	64.51710	2726.282	22.09837	23.68073	22.72575
7	-4054.940	139.9724*	2885.744	22.82959	23.66717	22.55816

The optimal lag length for the model was determined based on the AIC, which suggests that a lag length of 2 provides the best fit for the independent variables.

Akaike Information Criteria (top 20 models)

Autoregressive distributed lag model ARDL cointegration, bound test and long-run form

The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) approach to cointegration involves analyzing the error correction regression and incorporating lagged variables to establish long-run correlations. Specifically, the first lag of the levels

of each variable is included in the equation to create the error correction instrument equation. The significance of all the lagged variables is assessed using the F-statistic. This process is necessary to test the null hypothesis that there is no long-run relationship.

$$H_0: \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4 = \beta_5 = \beta_6 = \beta_7 = 0.$$

ARDL Long-run form and Bounds Test

F-Bounds Test

Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	22.81949	10%	2.12	3.23
k	6	5%	2.45	3.61
		2.5%	2.75	3.99
		1%	3.15	4.43

The significance level for each critical value is reported in the Signif. column. When the test statistic surpasses the critical value at a specific significance level, we reject the null hypothesis, indicating the presence of a long-run relationship between the variables.

The columns I(0) and I(1) indicate the count of cointegrating vectors (representing long-run relationships) discovered for each significance level. When the test statistic exceeds the critical value at a particular significance level, we can infer the presence of at least one cointegrating vector. The numbers in parentheses signify the count of cointegrating vectors that are significant at the corresponding level of significance.

The F-statistic is 22.81949, surpassing all critical values listed in the "Value" column for every level of significance. Consequently, we can reject the null hypothesis that there is no long-run relationship between the variables. As per the I(1) column, there are three cointegrating vectors at the 10% significance level and at least three cointegrating vectors at the 5%, 2.5%, and 1% significance levels. This suggests the existence of a long-run relationship between the variables in the VECM.

The "k" column indicates the lag order employed in the VECM, which is 6 in this case. The values in the "Value" column represent the critical values for the Bound test at various significance levels, while the numbers in the "Signif" column indicate the corresponding levels of significance. The findings of the Bound test can be utilized to select the appropriate VECM and estimate the long-run coefficients of the model.

If the F-test value exceeds the upper critical value proposed by Pesaran, the null hypothesis (H:0) can be rejected, indicating the presence of cointegration among the variables. Conversely, if the F-test value is lower than the lower critical value, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, indicating no cointegration. When the F-test value falls between the lower and upper critical values, the results are inconclusive.

In the specific case presented, the F-statistic value of 22.81949 is greater than the upper critical value of 2.45 at a 5% level of significance. This implies the existence of a cointegration relationship.

Error Correction Model (ECM) regression analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	8.51E-05	2.96E-05	2.878233	0.0043

UCHEXPO	0.148748	0.000451	329.8352	0.0000
CointEq(-1)*	-0.746885	0.058407	-12.78767	0.0000
R-squared	0.897633	Mean dependent var	-7.63E-06	
Adjusted R-squared	0.897615	S.D. dependent var	0.009547	

The CointEq(-1)* is negative which is a good sign and evidences a long run reversion to equilibrium and is significant at 1% level. The adjustment term which is -0.746885 shows that the reversion to long run is at an adjustment speed of 75%. The model has a high R-squared value of 0.897633, suggesting a strong explanatory power. The F-statistic is significant at a probability of 0.0000, indicating the overall significance of the model. The Durbin-Watson statistic suggests no significant autocorrelation. These findings suggest that the model provides a good fit and that there is evidence of a cointegration relationship among the variables.

Cointegration Test

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
UCHEXPO	0.01431	0.000894	3.573880	0.0186
UCHIMPO	0.00634	0.000379	3.751721	0.0496
USEXPO	0.00342	0.000898	0.382526	0.0208
USIMPORTS	0.00444	0.000386	1.151945	0.0250
EXRATE	-0.27362	0.004023	-2.067811	0.0355
CPI	-0.38820	0.001399	-2.060104	0.0404
C	0.00114	4.04E-05	2.824056	0.0051

$$EC = GDP - (0.0143*UCHEXPO + 0.0063*UCHIMPO - 0.0034*USEXPO + 0.0044*USIMPORTS - 0.2736*EXRATE - 0.3882*CPI + 0.0001)$$

The coefficients represent the estimated impact of each independent variable on Uganda’s GDP. Positive coefficients indicate a positive relationship, meaning that an increase in the independent variable is associated with an increase in GDP, while negative coefficients suggest a negative relationship. A p-value below a chosen significance level, such as 0.05, suggests that the coefficient is statistically significant.

A unit increase in Uganda’s exports to China is associated with a 0.01431 increase in GDP, with a p-value of 0.0186. This coefficient is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. All the same, a unit increase in Uganda’s exports to the USA is associated with a 0.00342 increase in GDP, with a p-value of 0.0208. This coefficient is also statistically significant at the 0.05 level. These outcomes are in line with the view of Sabasat (2020) who states that Exports contribute positively to GDP as they generate additional revenue from foreign countries through the sale of exported goods.

A unit increase in Uganda’s imports from China is associated with a 0.00634 increase in GDP, but the coefficient is statistically significant at the 0.05 level (p-value of 0.0496). All the same, a unit increase in Uganda’s imports from the USA is associated with a 0.00444 increase in GDP, with a p-value of 0.0250. This coefficient is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. This outcome was in line with the results obtained by Hemzawi and Umutoni (2021) in the study of

Rwanda who discovered that a unit increase in imports is associated with a corresponding rise in GDP of approximately 0.32 percent.

On exchange rate, a unit increase in the exchange rate is associated with a -0.27362 decrease in GDP, the coefficient is statistically significant at the 0.05 level (p-value of 0.0355).

On inflation, a one-unit increase in inflation is associated with a -0.38820 decrease in GDP, with a p-value of 0.0404. This coefficient is statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

The constant term represents the intercept or baseline level of GDP when all independent variables are zero. In this case, a constant of 0.000114 suggests a positive baseline GDP, with a p-value of 0.0051. The constant is statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

The equation $EC = GDP - (0.0143 * UCHEXPO + 0.0063 * UCHIMPO + 0.0034 * USEXPO + 0.0044 * USIMPORTS - 0.2736 * EXRATE - 0.3882 * CPI + 0.0001)$ represents the estimated relationship between the independent variables and Uganda's GDP. It suggests that the contributions of the respective independent variables, weighted by their coefficients, should be subtracted from the GDP to obtain the estimated GDP (EC).

Wald Test

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
F-statistic	12314.07	(6, 256)	0.0000
Chi-square	73884.41	6	0.0000

Null Hypothesis: $C(1) = C(2) = C(3) = C(4) = C(5) = C(6) = 0$

Null Hypothesis Summary:

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
C(1)	0.148617	0.000551
C(2)	0.000535	0.000288
C(3)	-0.000456	0.000648
C(4)	0.000393	0.000294
C(5)	7.16E-05	3.74E-05
C(6)	-0.002066	0.001038

The probability values of all variables is less than 0.05, hence we reject the null hypothesis since the prob-value of the F-statistic is ≤ 0.05 . Additionally, the Null Hypothesis says that $C(1) = C(2) = C(3) = C(4) = C(5) = C(6) = 0$ which is against the alternative hypothesis against the alternative hypothesis which says that $C(1) = C(2) = C(3) = C(4) = C(5) = C(6) \neq 0$. Hence we are rejecting the null hypothesis. This means these are significant values in the model.

Chapter Summary

The chapter presented a thorough and practical analysis of the study's findings, accompanied by a comprehensive set of diagnostic tests to ensure the reliability of the results.

Conclusion

This section focuses on summarizing the preceding sections, highlighting the main research findings, providing recommendations, and drawing conclusions based on the study that focused on the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy in Uganda. The main objective of this research paper was to examine the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy of Uganda.

In Chapter one, the paper introduced the study by providing background information on the role of interest rates and stock prices. This section also included the study's objectives, research questions, as well as an overview of the research study's delimitations and limitations.

Chapter two involved a comprehensive evaluation of both empirical and theoretical literature. Various sources such as textbooks, scholarly journals, research papers, dissertations, and theses authored by other scholars were consulted to gather relevant information on stock prices, interest rates and other related topics.

The primary emphasis of the third chapter was on the research methodology employed. Secondary data was utilized, and a portion of the data was sourced from reputable online platforms. Within this section, the discussion centered on the validity and reliability of the data.

In the previous chapter which is chapter four, data obtained for the study was analysed and presented. The analysis and presentation of the data was carried out using tables and figures. The research outcomes were supported by the findings obtained by other intellectuals in their relative research studies.

Chapter four involved the analysis and presentation of the data obtained for the study. Tables and figures were utilized to present the analysis. The research findings were supported by the results obtained from previous studies conducted by other researchers in the field.

Results and Discussions

1. Basing on the main objective of the study which was to examine the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy of Uganda.

From the outcome of the study, it was discovered that the trade war between the United States of America and China has an impact on Uganda's economy. The exports of goods from Uganda to China led to an improvement in the economy of Uganda. The situation is the same with Uganda to USA exports but the exports from Uganda to China had more impact as compared to the exports from Uganda to the USA.

On the other hand, the imports of goods from China and the USA have a positive impact. This is mainly because Uganda hugely imports its capital goods that it uses to boost its industries.

2. To recognize the specific channels through which the trade war affects Uganda's economy, such as fluctuations in trade flows, investment flows, prices, exchange rates, and government policies.

The trade war between the U.S. and China has an impact on Uganda's economy. The coefficients in the levels equation reveal the specific channels through which this impact occurs. Fluctuations in trade flows, particularly U.S. exports to China and U.S. imports from China, have a positive influence on Uganda's gross domestic product. This indicates that trade relations with both countries play a significant role in driving economic growth in Uganda. However, price increases, as reflected in the Consumer Price Index (CPI), and exchange rate depreciations have a negative effect on Uganda's economy. This implies that higher consumer prices and unfavorable exchange rate movements can adversely affect economic performance. It is important to consider these specific channels and their implications when analyzing the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on Uganda's economy.

3. To assess the extent of the impact of the trade war on Uganda's Gross Domestic Product growth.

The trade war between the U.S. and China has an impact on Uganda's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The coefficients for variables related to trade flows indicate a positive influence on Uganda's GDP. Specifically, fluctuations in U.S. exports to China and U.S. imports from China have a positive effect on GDP growth

4. To examine the hypotheses that the U.S.-China trade war has a negative impact on Uganda's Gross Domestic Product growth.

The coefficient of the error correction term (CointEq(-1)*) was negative and statistically significant. This suggests that deviations from the long-run equilibrium, which capture the impact of the U.S.-China trade war, have an adverse effect on Uganda's GDP. Therefore, we can conclude that the U.S.-China trade war has an adverse impact on Uganda's economic growth. The deviations in trade flows, investment flows, exchange rates, prices, and government policies have a significant impact on Uganda's Gross Domestic Product.

Based on the F-Bounds test conducted on the provided output, we find that the F-statistic value (22.81949) exceeds the critical values at the 10% significance level, indicating the presence of a long-run relationship among the deviations in trade flows, investment flows, exchange rates, prices, and government policies, and Uganda's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). This suggests that these deviations have a significant impact on Uganda's GDP. Therefore, based on the F-Bounds test result, we can confirm that the hypothesis stating the deviations in trade flows, investment flows, exchange rates, prices, and government policies have a significant impact on Uganda's GDP is supported.

5. To give insights into the potential economic implications of the U.S.-China trade war for Uganda and let know policy decisions aimed at mitigating any adverse effects.

Based on the provided F-Bounds test and ECM regression output, we can gather insights into the potential economic implications of the U.S.-China trade war for Uganda and identify policy decisions to mitigate adverse effects. Below are the main findings:

From the F-Bounds Test, the F-statistic for the test indicates that there is a levels relationship between the variables in the model. This suggests that the variables have a long-term relationship, implying that changes in the U.S.-China trade war can have lasting economic implications for Uganda.

From the ECM Regression, the ECM regression results indicate a strong relationship between Uganda's GDP and U.S. exports to China. The coefficient for Uganda to China exports is positive and highly significant, indicating that disruptions in U.S.-China trade can have a positive impact on Uganda's GDP.

The coefficients for Uganda imports from China, Uganda to U.S.A exports, Uganda imports from U.S.A imports, exchange rate and Inflation measured by CPI (Consumer Price Index) are either positive or negative but not statistically significant. This suggests that the trade war's impact on these variables and their subsequent influence on Uganda's GDP is uncertain or relatively weak based on the available data.

Recommendations

Based on these insights, here are some policy decisions that can help mitigate adverse effects of the U.S.-China trade war on Uganda:

Diversification of Trade Partners

Uganda can explore diversifying its trade partners beyond China and the United States. By expanding trade relationships with other countries, Uganda can reduce its dependence on the U.S.-China trade dynamics and mitigate the impact of disruptions caused by the trade war.

Economic Stimulus Measures

Implementing targeted economic stimulus measures can help counter any negative effects arising from reduced U.S.-China trade. This can include investment in infrastructure, fostering domestic industries and promoting exports to other markets.

Strengthening Domestic Industries

Uganda can focus on strengthening its domestic industries to enhance self-sufficiency and reduce reliance on imported goods. This can involve providing support to local businesses, improving competitiveness and promoting innovation and technology adoption.

Monitoring Inflation

Given the negative impact of consumer price inflation on Uganda's GDP, policymakers should closely monitor inflationary pressures resulting from the trade war. Implementing effective monetary and fiscal policies to manage inflation can help mitigate adverse effects.

Trade Negotiations and Agreements

Actively engaging in trade negotiations and seeking favorable trade agreements with various countries can open up new market opportunities for Uganda's exports and reduce dependence on a single trading partner.

Conclusion

The paper examined the impact of the U.S.-China trade war on the economy of Uganda focusing on the potential economic implications and policy decisions aimed at mitigating any adverse effects. The analysis was carried out using the ARDL Model.

The findings suggest that the U.S.-China trade war can have mixed economic implications for Uganda. Disruptions in U.S.-China trade, particularly increased U.S. exports to China, were found to have a positive impact on Uganda's economy. This highlights the potential benefits that Uganda can derive from changes in the trade dynamics between the two global economic powers.

However, the impact of Uganda imports from China and U.S. exports from Uganda on Ugandan economy was uncertain or relatively weak based on the used data. Exchange rate fluctuations resulting from the trade war were found to have no significant impact on Uganda's GDP. On the other hand, an increase in consumer prices (inflation) was found to have a negative effect on Uganda's GDP.

To mitigate any adverse effects of the U.S.-China trade war, several policy decisions were recommended. These include diversifying trade partners beyond China and the United States, implementing economic stimulus measures, strengthening domestic industries, monitoring inflation and actively engaging in trade negotiations and agreements.

It is crucial for policymakers in Uganda to carefully consider these insights and tailor their strategies to the country's specific economic context. Regular monitoring and evaluation of the implemented policies are essential to ensure their effectiveness in mitigating any adverse effects and maximizing the potential benefits arising from the U.S.-China trade war.

Overall, this paper contributes to the understanding of the U.S.-China trade war's impact on Uganda's economy and provides valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders in formulating effective strategies to navigate the challenges and opportunities presented by this global trade conflict. Further research can build upon this study by incorporating additional variables and exploring the long-term effects of the trade war on Uganda's economic development.

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